

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health.

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

DELIVERABLE 1.3 v1

STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT AND CONTEXT ANALYSIS

WP1

Authors: Taícia Marques and Ruth Lowry

Summary Sheet

Deliverable Number	D 1.3
Deliverable Name	Stakeholders' engagement and context analysis
Full Project Title	CITY-MOVE: City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health
Responsible Author(s)	Taícia Marques ¹ , Ruth Lowry ²
Contributing Partner(s)	¹ Universidad Nacional Agraria La Molina; ² Ulster University
Peer Review	-
Contractual Delivery Date	June 30 2025
Actual Delivery Date	June 30 2025
Status	-
Dissemination level	Open access
Version	v.1
No. of Pages	131
WP/Task related to the milestone	WP1/ Task 1.2 and 1.3
WP/Task responsible	WP1/ Taícia Marques
Document ID	
Abstract	-

Legal Disclaimer

CITY-MOVE is funded by the European Union (EUROPEAN HEALTH AND DIGITAL EXECUTIVE AGENCY-HADEA, GAP-101136358) and Innovate UK (10109214). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, Horizon EU or Innovate UK. The granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

List of Figures	4
List of Tables	5
List of Abbreviations.....	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. CITY-MOVE GAPPA.....	8
2. Stakeholder mapping	32
2.1 Tools and methods for collecting data.....	32
2.2 RESULTS	36
3. CORE CONTEXT ELEMENTS.....	64
3.1 TOOLS AND METHODS FOR COLLECTING DATA	64
3.2 RESULTS	65
4. GENDER – INCLUSIVITY – DIVERSITY (GID)	1
4.1 GID RESULTS	1
5. REFERENCES	2

List of Figures

Figure 1: Images from workshop in different cities.....	33
Figure 2. Antwerp’s 1st stakeholders map.....	39
Figure 3. Antwerp’s 2nd stakeholders map.	42
Figure 4. Bogota’s stakeholders map.	46
Figure 5. Kampala’s stakeholders map.....	51
Figure 6. Lima’s stakeholder map.....	54
Figure 7. Ljubljana’s stakeholders map.	58
Figure 8. Rotterdam’s stakeholders map.	62

List of Tables

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPa summary	9
Table 2: Stakeholders mapping summary	37
Table 3: CITY-MOVE Core Context Elements Summary	66
Table 4: Strengths Between Cities Summary	106
Table 5: Weaknesses Between Cities Summary	113
Table 6: Opportunities Between Cities Summary	116
Table 7: Threats Between Cities Summary	123

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
GID	Gender, inclusivity and diversity
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
NGO	Non-Government Organization
PA	Physical Activity
SAW	Stakeholder Assessment Workshop
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The WP1 is responsible for creating a cross-contextual framework to replicate health interventions in cities that may contribute to the reduction of non-communicable diseases cases. During the timeframe of the CITY-MOVE project, five different activities are related to this work-package. Deliverable 1.3 reports on the completed activities related to **T.1.2 -A stakeholder assessment and analysis in each city for each intervention** and **T1.3 -Core context elements** in each one of the six partner cities in CITY-MOVE. The data was collected by the CITY-MOVE contact points following the instructions provided by WP1 in the “Stakeholder Assessment and Core Context Elements Guide” (see D1.3 Supplementary material).

This report contains summaries with complete information about stakeholders and core context elements for the late interventions in the six CITY-MOVE cities. Sensitive information was left out the report. With concern to early interventions, the depth of data varies between cities due to the various stages of development each intervention is at and the availability of appropriate information.

1. CITY-MOVE GAPPA

The early and late interventions which form the focus of CITY-MOVE are part of each city's larger strategic development which may or may not have population physical health as the primary driver. One of the project goals is to generate transferrable lessons on a comprehensive approach to city-GAPPA, by studying 13 interventions (7 late and 6 early interventions which come from all GAPPA domains) and considering other city-GAPPA interventions occurring in these 6 cities. To do this, with the support of WP7, the 13 focus interventions were mapped against the 20 types of intervention activities found in the GAPPA framework and visualize any linkages of the 13 focus interventions to other GAPPA interventions that are ongoing in the city.

- The domain, *Create an active society – social norms and attitudes*, received 13 indications, mainly focusing on “1.2- Conduct national and community-based campaigns to enhance awareness and understanding of, and appreciation for, the social, economic, and environmental co-benefits of physical activity” (6 mentions).
- The domain, *Create active environments – spaces and places* received 30 indications, with special attention given to “2.4 Strengthen access to good-quality public and green open spaces, green networks, recreational spaces and sports amenities” shown in almost all interventions (11 mentions).
- The domain, *Create active people – programmes and opportunities*, was the most often cited (34 times). Each type of activity from 3.1 to 3.5 were reported with at least 5 interventions, while 3.6, Implement whole-of-community initiatives, at the city, town or community levels, was not mentioned by any intervention.
- The domain, *Create active systems – governance and policy enablers* was mentioned 16 times and related to only 5 from the 13 interventions (see Table 1 for full information).

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.1 Implement best practice communication campaigns, linked with community-based programmes		The "Bewegen op Verwijzing" (BOV) uses targeted campaigns to raise awareness of PA benefits, directing people to local resources like certified coaches.		Street intimidation project							Physical Activity Promotion Program for a Healthy Life
Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.2 Conduct national and community-based campaigns to enhance awareness and understanding of, and appreciation for, the social, economic, and environmental co-benefits of physical activity				Biking school plus	The maps are distributed through the neighbourhood paper.	The plan is to create community-based campaigns targeting the Tarwewijk					

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.3 Implement regular mass participation initiatives in public spaces, engaging entire communities							Rotterdam Marathon			Educational institutions carry out Sports Olympics, Spring Games events	
Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.4 Strengthen pre- and in-service training of professionals, within and outside the health sector		The intervention involves training exercise coaches, as well as health professionals to conduct the referrals			Collaborations are sought with health professionals, municipality presentative gives presentation to health professionals in Rotterdam	The plan is also to seek collaboration with health professionals					
Create active environments – spaces and places 2.1 Strengthen the integration of urban and transport planning policies to prioritize the principles of compact, mixed-land use, at all levels of government					Green and existing active infrastructure are combined	Green and existing active infrastructure will be combined	RotterdamLoopt, Mobility approach, Fietskoers 2025				Policy - Bike lines in the independica

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
Create active environments – spaces and places 2.2 Improve the level of service provided by walking and cycling network infrastructure				Pedestrian Policy Plan	Community and policy efforts for improved infrastructure	Community and policy efforts for improved infrastructure					
Create active environments – spaces and places 2.3 Accelerate implementation of policy actions to improve road safety and the personal safety of pedestrians, cyclists, people engaged in other forms of mobility				Slow speed routes	Participants can escalate unsafe situation on the route to the municipality for improved policymaking	Setting up a new intervention shows policymakers there is momentum and need for policy actions.					
Create active environments – spaces and places 2.4 Strengthen access to good-quality public and green open spaces, green networks, recreational spaces and sports amenities	The intervention involves placemaking at a former hospital (Stuivenbergziekenhuis), which is now transforming into a public space/park.				The interventions target various groups, including children, elderly, people with mental health issues etc to participate in physical activity in green spaces.	The plan for the intervention is to target the least active and reduce inequality in physical activity.		The plan is to sensitize the Greenbelt as a new area for physical and recreational activities in the district of Independencia.	The programme provides free and open access sports facilities to the residents of Villa María del Triunfo (VMT) district.	VMT Sports Complex allows free and open access to school children of all ages and with different abilities, providing a space with safe, universal, and equitable access.	

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
<p>Create active environments – spaces and places</p> <p>2.5 Strengthen the policy, regulatory and design guidelines and frameworks, at the national and subnational levels</p>				Garden/living streets (Ant breekt uit)	Green and healthy neighbourhood approach, policy approach of different departments, was involved in the development of the intervention	Green and healthy neighbourhood approach will be involved in the development of this intervention through an appointed neighbourhood coordinator		The Greenbelt was proposed by the Concerted Local Development Plan (2018-2022-2025) as a Landscape Protection Zone reinforcing their environmental and recreational purposes. Part of its natural ecosystem is conserved by law and one of its forest parks is already regulated as public park. These efforts are aligned with the Comprehensive Plan for the Greenbelt of Independencia 2022-2030 (not approved yet).		Executive Directorial Resolution N° 001- 2021-MTC/34 strengthens the Legacy's internal guidelines to promote sports facilities such as the VMT Sports Complex to be open to the community and schools in the area, so that children can be physically active.	

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
<p>Create active people – programmes and opportunities</p> <p>3.1 Strengthen provision of good-quality physical education and more positive experiences and opportunities for active recreation, sports and play</p>	The intervention intends to co-create activities with teenagers to engage in physical activity.			Ecoschool & Green feet daycare	Some initiatives on the map are playgrounds, and there are specific activities for children in some other green initiatives (ex. School gardening).	The intervention aims to co-create an environment for positive experience and opportunities for active recreation for all groups, including children.		The programme provides free and open access sports facilities to VMT residents.	The program improves the provision of quality physical education services in educational institutions lacking adequate infrastructure, makes recreational and sports facilities available to the community to support the participation of vulnerable populations, such as schoolchildren with diverse abilities.	Municipal Programs in the District	

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
<p>Create active people – programmes and opportunities</p> <p>3.2 Implement and strengthen systems of patient assessment and counselling on increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviour</p>		By embedding physical activity promotion into healthcare settings, using personalized approaches, and providing ongoing support, it strengthens efforts to increase physical activity and reduce sedentary behaviour in a sustainable and impactful way.	The Health Kiosk deploys an exercise coach to support people in the neighbourhood to reduce sedentary behaviour.	Halt2Diabetes	Social and healthcare provider refer to the map and initiatives for physical activity.	The plan is to involve social and healthcare providers in a later stage in the development of the intervention.					
<p>Create active people – programmes and opportunities</p> <p>3.3 Enhance provision of, and opportunities for, more physical activity programmes and promotion in parks and other natural environments as well as in private and public workplaces, community centres, recreation and sports facilities and faith-based centres</p>	BraveMove is seeking to provide opportunities and provision of physical activity programs in a public space in Antwerpen-Noord.				The routes are connected to green spaces.	The intervention will likely improve green spaces in the neighbourhood for improved physical activity.	Gardening initiatives	The different spaces within the Greenbelt (forest parks, coastal desert and lomas ecosystem zones) provide the community with opportunities to engage in recreational and physical activities.		Provision of quality physical education services in educational institutions lacking adequate infrastructure, makes recreational and sports facilities available to the community to	

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
										support the participation of vulnerable populations, such as schoolchildren with diverse abilities.	
<p>Create active people - programmes and opportunities</p> <p>3.4 Enhance the provision of, and opportunities for, appropriately tailored programmes and services aimed at increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviour in older adults</p>			The Health Kiosk deploys an exercise coach to support people in the neighbourhood to reduce sedentary behaviour. It has also hosted activities specifically for older adults.		There is specific programming for older adults, e.g. walking groups, and one of the initiatives is called 'gardening for elderly'	The intervention aims to co-create an environment for positive experience and opportunities for active recreation for all groups, including older adults.					
<p>Create active people - programmes and opportunities</p> <p>3.5 Strengthen the development and implementation of programmes and services, across various community settings, to engage with, and increase the opportunities for,</p>			Various organisations have hosted events and activities in the Health Kiosk, to engage with opportunities for physical activity in the least active groups.		The social and healthcare provides refer the most vulnerable people to the intervention	The intervention aims to co-create an environment for positive experience and opportunities for active recreation for least active groups, not	Neighbourhood approach	Local community has actively engaged in initiatives such as developing organic gardens, tree planting, trekking routes in the Greenbelt.		Provision of quality physical education services in educational institutions lacking adequate infrastructure, makes recreational	

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
physical activity in the least active groups						clear yet on which one the focus will be or that it will be community broad.				and sports facilities available to the community to support the participation of vulnerable populations, such as schoolchildren with diverse abilities.	
3.6 Implement whole-of-community initiatives, at the city, town or community levels											
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.1 Strengthen policy frameworks, leadership and governance systems, at the national and subnational levels					A new municipality neighbourhood approach is developed at the municipality level, which includes climate adaptation, mobility, and health departments.	A new municipality neighbourhood approach is developed at the municipality level, which includes climate adaptation, mobility, and health departments.	Neighbourhood approach, purpose-driven approach			Executive Directorial Resolution N° 001- 2021-MTC/34 establishes the “Guidelines for the opening of the Andrés Avelino Cáceres Sports Complex in VMT of the Legacy Special	Visits to the Sports Complex

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
										Project". Its purpose is to guarantee that sports complex achieves social sustainability over time, serving both for the practice of high competition sports, as well as for the realization of sports and recreational activities for the benefit of the community.	
<p>Create active systems – governance and policy enablers</p> <p>4.2 Enhance data systems and capabilities at the national and, where appropriate, subnational levels</p>		BOV collects data on referrals, enabling evidence-based adjustments and ensuring the program meets local health needs. Data is analysed at the subnational					Neighbourhood profile website				Visits to the Legacy

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
		level to identify disparities and optimize program delivery in different communities.									
<p>Create active systems – governance and policy enablers</p> <p>4.3 Strengthen the national and institutional research and evaluation capacity and stimulate the application of digital technologies and innovation</p>		The program has been subject to research and evaluation by academic institutions in Belgium, focusing on its impact on physical activity levels and health outcomes. In some regions, Digital platforms are used for managing referrals and monitoring participants' progress, increasing efficiency and scalability.			An EU consortium developed a value model to evaluate initiatives from De Groene Connective.	Erasmus University Rotterdam is involved in the development of the intervention.					Workshops and Classes

Table 1: CITY-MOVE GAPPA summary

CITY-MOVE GAPPA Mapping	Antwerp				Rotterdam			Lima			
	Early	Late	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Sport Facilities Loan	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	GIRL	Movement Referral	Health Kiosk		Green Connection	Green Walking Route		Independencia Greenbelt		Sports Complex at VMT	
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.4 Escalate advocacy efforts to increase awareness and knowledge of, and engagement in, joint action at the global, regional and national levels					Those involved in the intervention are involved in advocacy efforts, including city-wide projects, but also international collaborations.	The aim is had those involved do the same as with the existing intervention.					
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.5 Strengthen financing mechanisms to secure sustained implementation of national and subnational action and the development of the enabling systems		The intervention is supported by funding from the Flemish government, which ensures its sustained implementation.					GALA-Budget (healthy and active living agreement budget)				Sports Events

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
<p>Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.1 Implement best practice communication campaigns, linked with community-based programmes</p>				School of Public health weekly walk			Ljubljana Marathon,			Schools on My Neighbourhood	
<p>Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.2 Conduct national and community-based campaigns to enhance awareness and understanding of, and appreciation for, the social, economic, and environmental co-benefits of physical activity</p>		The event is spearheaded by KCCA and cyclists to promote sustainable transportation and healthier lives by lowering air pollution levels and promoting active mobility in Kampala.		National physical activity day	The plan is to develop a mobile app to motivate younger people to engage in PA. Designed for the Ljubljana area, the app will use interactive challenges and fascinating local facts to encourage users to explore and move more within the city.	The WATW event is one of the Major Sports and Recreational Events of the Sports Strategy of the Municipality of Ljubljana. The event is used as an annual campaign that emphasizes the health and social benefits of PA.	Franja Marathon(c)			Sports in Life	
<p>Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.3 Implement regular mass participation initiatives in public spaces, engaging entire communities</p>	The Car-Free Day event in Kampala transforms public spaces such as the City Square and streets into active zones, encouraging mass participation			TeamMatooke		WATW exemplifies this indicator by promoting free, inclusive, and community-wide participation in physical activity. The event's success is supported by an easy registration process and	European Employees' Sports Games in Ljubljanad)			Paralympic Sports Performance	

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
	in walking, aerobics and cycling while fostering good attitudes to engagement in physical activity and environmental protection initiatives.					proactive communication with the general public, kindergartens, and schools, ensuring timely awareness and engagement. Additionally, its strong social and cultural elements significantly contribute to the high participation rates, fostering a sense of community and shared tradition.					
Create an active society – social norms and attitudes 1.4 Strengthen pre- and in-service training of professionals, within and outside the health sector				Joe Walker Uganda			Let's get Ljubljana moving				

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor			Walk Game App	Walk along the wire			CEFE Happiness Centres	
<p>Create active environments – spaces and places 2.1 Strengthen the integration of urban and transport planning policies to prioritize the principles of compact, mixed-land use, at all levels of government</p>			<p>The Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) corridor integrates active mobility into urban planning, promoting mixed-land use where walking and cycling are prioritized. It supports a compact city design that reduces dependence on motorized transport, enhances accessibility to key areas, and encourages sustainable urban development at multiple governance levels.</p>	Digital bikes; rent a bike			Sport Islands				
<p>Create active environments – spaces and places 2.2 Improve the level of service provided by walking and cycling network infrastructure</p>		<p>The intervention advocates for safe cycling in Kampala and this includes the provision of safer cycling lanes that are of good</p>		Fun Cycling	<p>The app is currently in the conceptual phase, and its development could lead to enhancements in the walking and</p>	<p>WATW relies on accessible paths and green spaces, underscoring the value of maintaining and expanding urban</p>			<p>Bogota City Council Agreement to Ciclovias and Cycle Routes</p>		

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
			quality in Kampala city.		cycling infrastructure to support its interactive features. For example, the infrastructure may be adapted to accommodate app challenges and tasks, such as installing signs, fun fact plaques, or QR codes along the routes. Ensuring these routes remain engaging and accessible year-round would require regular maintenance and updates to keep them in good condition and aligned with the app's evolving content.	infrastructure for walking and recreational activities. The MOL in collaboration with other public institutions reviews and improves safety measures along the routes.					

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
<p>Create active environments – spaces and places 2.3 Accelerate implementation of policy actions to improve road safety and the personal safety of pedestrians, cyclists, people engaged in other forms of mobility</p>	<p>The car free day is a mass participation event during which there is advocacy for road safety for pedestrians, cyclists and other vulnerable road users such as persons with disabilities</p>		<p>The Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) corridor in Kampala contributes to this GAPPA domain by providing dedicated pedestrian walkways and bicycle lanes, reducing conflicts with motorized traffic. It enhances road safety by minimizing the risk of accidents, promoting safe mobility for pedestrians and cyclists, and supporting policy actions that prioritize active transportation infrastructure.</p>								

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
<p>Create active environments – spaces and places 2.4 Strengthen access to good-quality public and green open spaces, green networks, recreational spaces and sports amenities</p>		<p>The intervention allows free access to bicycles for a majority of riders who participate in the event, as well as the opportunity to ride freely in Kampala.</p>		<p>The app will serve as a guide, directing users to supportive infrastructure such as "sport islands," outdoor fitness areas, and multipurpose playgrounds. By showcasing these spaces through challenges and interactive features, the app will raise awareness of their availability and encourage regular visits. This increased engagement will enhance the visibility and utilization of these facilities, contributing to their value within the community and fostering a deeper appreciation for Ljubljana's natural and recreational resources.</p>	<p>WATW utilizes the Path of Remembrance and Comradeship, which is a well-maintained scenic green network that encircles Ljubljana, to promote physical activity and community engagement. The event aligns with the strategy's goal to enhance access to green and urban sports areas, aiming for 2m² of recreational space per capita by 2028. The city has committed to creating supportive infrastructure like "sport islands", outdoor fitness areas, and multipurpose playgrounds,</p>		<p>Architectural proposal that includes green areas within the CEFEs</p>	<p>Cycle Infrastructure connected to city parks</p>			

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action		Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor			Walk Game App		Walk along the wire		
							ensuring broad access to spaces that encourage regular physical activity.				
Create active environments – spaces and places 2.5 Strengthen the policy, regulatory and design guidelines and frameworks, at the national and subnational levels			In Kampala, the NMT pilot corridor on Namirembe and Luwum streets is one of the implementations influenced by the NMT policy/guidelines. However, enforcement and adherence remain challenges, with issues such as encroachment affecting its effectiveness						Bogota City Council Agreement		
Create active people – programmes and opportunities 3.1 Strengthen provision of good-quality physical education and more positive experiences and opportunities for active recreation, sports and play					The intervention seeks to promote physical activity among teenagers and young adults in an engaging and educational way.			zMIGAJ	Programs provided by the IDRD and the Secretariat of Culture	Recreovía	

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action		Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor			Walk Game App		Walk along the wire		
Create active people – programmes and opportunities 3.2 Implement and strengthen systems of patient assessment and counselling on increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviour								Wiggle your way to exercise		Take care, Be Happy	
Create active people – programmes and opportunities 3.3 Enhance provision of, and opportunities for, more physical activity programmes and promotion in parks and other natural environments as well as in private and public workplaces, community centres, recreation and sports facilities and faith-based centres	The Car Free Day encourages the uptake of physical activity in a simple, safe and inclusive outdoor environment, in the streets, something very rare in Kampala.				The app will enhance opportunities for physical activity by promoting programs and activities primarily in parks, natural environments, and outdoor sports areas. Users will be guided to these locations through interactive challenges and engaging content, encouraging exploration and active use of these spaces. While the app will initially focus on outdoor activities, it has the potential to expand in the future to include indoor options.			National sports programmes: Little Sunshine, Golden Sunshine, Punch, School Sports Competitions,			

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
<p>Create active people – programmes and opportunities 3.4 Enhance the provision of, and opportunities for, appropriately tailored programmes and services aimed at increasing physical activity and reducing sedentary behaviour in older adults</p>					While older adults are not the primary target audience of the app, they are welcome to use it if they wish.	The event offers shorter, less demanding recreational routes, allowing older participants to walk or engage in less strenuous activities. They also often join alongside their grandchildren, fostering intergenerational bonding. Additionally, associations for the elderly participate, ensuring a supportive and inclusive environment.	Let's Learn to Swim, Hooray for Leisure and others.				
<p>Create active people – programmes and opportunities 3.5 Strengthen the development and implementation of programmes and services, across various community settings, to engage with, and increase the opportunities for, physical activity in the least active groups</p>	The Car free day provides a platform for less active people in Kampala including women, and corporate workers to walk and engage in moderate		By providing dedicated pedestrian walkways and cycling lanes, the NMT corridor promotes active mobility as part of daily routines, benefiting individuals who may not engage			The event is designed to be inclusive, offering support and resources for those with lower fitness levels. It features shorter, less demanding routes, making it accessible for seniors and		Recreovia / Activities provided by the IDRD			

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor	Walk Game App		Walk along the wire	CEFE Happiness Centres		Ciclovia		
		physical activity such as aerobics, which is uncommon in their typical day.		in structured exercise.		individuals with limited mobility. By encouraging participation from various community groups, including associations for the elderly, the event fosters a supportive environment. It also promotes intergenerational activity, making it easier for families to be active together and helping to engage less active individuals.					
3.6 Implement whole-of-community initiatives, at the city, town or community levels											
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.1 Strengthen policy frameworks, leadership and governance systems, at the national and subnational levels							Ljubljana is Sport			Recreation Pathway	

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action	Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor			Walk Game App	Walk along the wire			CEFE Happiness Centres	
<p>Create active systems – governance and policy enablers</p> <p>4.2 Enhance data systems and capabilities at the national and, where appropriate, subnational levels</p>			<p>Collection of data about the Non-Motorized transport corridor can enable learning from the reports to enable scale up of the project sustainably.</p>		<p>At this stage, it is still undecided, but the app could potentially collect anonymized data on physical activity patterns, route preferences, and engagement levels. This information could help policymakers and planners assess infrastructure usage, improve physical activity programs, and guide investments to address gaps in service delivery.</p>	<p>The MOL partners with Timing Ljubljana, a specialized sports organization that offers technological support for sports, manages sports events, provides electronic timing, handles computer processing of results, and offers IT services. In addition, they organize and conduct sports programs and rent technical equipment. Timing Ljubljana is responsible for collecting data related to participation, scores, and conducting statistical analysis of this data.</p>				<p>Bike School</p>	

CITY-MOVE Mapping	GAPPA	Kampala				Ljubljana			Bogota		
		Early	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other	Early	Late	Other
Strategic objectives - Action		Car Free	Monthly Cycling	NMT Corridor			Walk Game App		Walk along the wire		
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.3 Strengthen the national and institutional research and evaluation capacity and stimulate the application of digital technologies and innovation											Take care, Be Happy
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.4 Escalate advocacy efforts to increase awareness and knowledge of, and engagement in, joint action at the global, regional and national levels		One of the goals of the event is advocacy for 1) road safety and 2) good air quality in Kampala	The main goal of the intervention is advocacy efforts, to increase awareness about cycling in Kampala.								Street Vendors
Create active systems – governance and policy enablers 4.5 Strengthen financing mechanisms to secure sustained implementation of national and subnational action and the development of the enabling systems											

2. Stakeholder mapping

CITY-MOVE defined stakeholders as *people and groups who are responsible for or affected by health, healthcare-related decisions, physical activity interventions and physical activity-related decisions. They may include, not only, those directly involved in the development of guidelines, policies, strategies, planning and implementing the interventions, but also those involved in preparing research, conducting research, dissemination activities or implementing that evidence.* Initially, a list of ten types or categories of stakeholders was adapted from the work of Petkovic et al. (2023) incorporating the majority of possible types of stakeholders that should be part of CITY-MOVE interventions. The final version, containing eleven categories, is the result of a consulting process with the wider CITY-MOVE research team to ensure that each was culturally meaningful and inclusive to the 6 cities. Therefore, the categories defined are Payers or Funders of research; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers; Policy makers; Researchers; Product developers; Program managers; Providers; Active community members and organizations; Patients, Patient caregivers, patient advocates/organizations; General Public; Logistics or support. The full description of each one can be found in D1.3 Supplementary material. Stakeholders mapping is the process of identifying, visualizing, and prioritizing stakeholders by analysing their role, engagement, influence and interest in each intervention. The stakeholder's map is a living tool; it can be adapted during the project, especially with information regarding the people that represent each stakeholder group and the relationship between them. The objective of the stakeholder mapping exercise was to support the progressive comprehension of inter-organizational governance structures within each CITY-MOVE intervention.

2.1 Tools and methods for collecting data

To aid the consistent gathering and organizing of mapping information the “Data collection tool 1.1- Stakeholder map table v.1” and the “Data collection tool 1.2 - Open interview guide” were created and provided to CITY-MOVE contact points and researchers (see complementary document “Stakeholders Assessment and Core Context elements Guide”). Moreover the “Stakeholder Assessment and Core Context Elements Guide” gave the instructions and suggestions for developing stakeholders assessment workshop withing late interventions (Figure 1). A training workshop was delivered at the CITY-MOVE kick-off meeting held in Bogota, Columbia in May 2024. The workshop was delivered by the primary authors and researchers from each city attended. This provided an opportunity for the research teams to pilot materials and role play potential facilitation logistics and concerns as a group.

Figure 1: Images from workshop in different cities

Antwerp
Late intervention – Health Kiosk

Antwerp
Late intervention – Exercise on Prescription

Bogota
Late intervention - Ciclovía

Bogota
Early intervention - Happiness Centres

Kampala
Late intervention - Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor

Lima
Late intervention - Program to lend facilities of the Villa María del Triunfo (VMT) Sports Complex to Schools.

2.2 RESULTS

CITY-MOVE contact points mapped their main stakeholders for the late intervention, and, where possible, for the early intervention. Table 2 lists the name of the stakeholders, the type of organization (public, private or other), their role in the intervention, the CITY-MOVE category and the level of involvement in the intervention. The quantity of stakeholders mapped varies from 8 to 26 in late interventions and from none to 18 in early interventions. Regarding late interventions, most of the stakeholders are providers (50), followed by Program Managers (27), Policy Makers (21), Active community members and organizations (17) and Logistics or Support (16). Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers of Services and prevention projects (7) usually overlap roles with Policy Makers, Providers and/ or Program Managers. Patients and the General Public are mentioned only 4 times each in late interventions.

All late interventions present a massive prevalence of public organizations. In Antwerp and Kampala, it calls the attention the large presence of “other” types of organizations, mostly represented by NGO and citizens associations or representatives. All cities mentioned the presence of private stakeholders. Their role was associated to stakeholder types: provider, product developer, logistics and support, active communities’ members and organizations or general public.

Regarding early interventions, in some cases, even though stakeholders could be mapped, researchers could not classify them according to CITY-MOVE categories yet. This information should be collected during the development of the Living-labs in each city.

With the information from Table 2 and the reports from each city, we elaborate Stakeholder Maps for each late intervention. A first version was sent to each team for validation, and the results are presented in Figure 2 to Figure 8. These diagrams allow us to visually represent the actors, their typology and the relationships between them, for example, the city of Lima has more neutral than collaborative relationships due to the nature of the intervention, the relationships in Bogota are concentrated in the IDR which is the leading institution that manages the intervention, while in Rotterdam the relationships are more diversified.

Table 2: Stakeholders mapping summary

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Leve of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Late intervention – Health Kiosk				
UAntwerpen	Public	Research and strategy support	Researchers	High
Logo Antwerpen	Public/NGO	Health promotion and education	Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers; Providers	High
Community Health Worker	Other (Community-based)	Gives advice at Health Kiosk and signposts to healthcare system	Active community members and organizations; Providers	High
Instroom academy	NGO/Other	Educational support and integration	Active community members and organizations	High
Zermatt	Private	Community centre on the same square as the Health Kiosk. Provides affordable meals, every Tuesday and Wednesday fresh soup for 0.50	Active community members and organizations	High
Stad Antwerpen	Public	City-level coordination and policy	Policy makers; Program managers	High
District Borgerhout	Public	Local level government support	Policy makers; Program managers	High
Health Kiosk coordinator	Other	Health coordination and outreach	Program managers	High
SAAMO	NGO/Other	Community engagement and welfare	Active community members and organizations; Program managers; Providers	Medium
Zelfstandig eerstlijns psycholoog (Independent first-line psychologist)	Private	Mental health support	Providers	Medium
Dietist	Private	Nutritional guidance	Providers	Medium
Exercise coach	Private	Physical health and fitness support	Providers	Medium
STW Steunpunt Tewerkstelling (STW Employment Support Centre)	Public/NGO	Employment support	Program managers; Providers	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Late intervention – Health Kiosk				
Welzijnsoverleg (Welfare consultation)	Public/NGO	Social welfare meetings	Providers	Medium
Werkhuys	NGO/Other	Community work and training	Active community members and organizations	Medium
ELZA	Other	Health and welfare services	Providers	Medium
EMSA H4L (Heart for Life)	Other	Voluntary medical students provide free heart checkups and advice at health kiosk	Providers	Medium
Conventie eerstlijns 4	Public	Primary healthcare	Providers; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	Medium
KDG Hogeschool	Public	Research and education support	Researchers	Medium
Groothandel Claessens	Private	Supply of fresh produce	Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	Medium
Wijkgezondheidscentrum 't spoor	Public	Community doctors practice in the neighbourhood which works with Health Kiosk	Providers	Low
Ligo Antwerpen	NGO/Other	Education and literacy support	Providers	Low
Sporting A Wijkmedewerker	Public/Other	Sports promotion for local communities	Program managers; Providers	Low
HTD	Private	Technology support for health initiatives	Product developers	Low
KOTK	NGO/Other	Cancer support	Patients, patient caregivers, patient advocates/ organizations	Low
Rataplan	NGO/Other	Cultural engagement and events	Active community members and organizations	Low
Mutualiteit	Other	Health insurance and patient support	Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	Low

The Stakeholder Map for Antwerp's 1st late intervention is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Antwerp's 1st stakeholders map.

ANTWERP - Health Kiosk

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Late intervention – Exercise on Prescription				
Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven	Public	Strategic health institution in "Exercise on Prescription" intervention	Providers; Program managers	High
Referrers (Verwijzer)	Other	Health professionals referring patients in the "Exercise on Prescription" intervention	Providers	High
Patients	Other	Beneficiaries of the "Exercise on Prescription" intervention	Patients, patient caregivers, patient advocates/ organizations	High
Department of Care, Flemish Government	Public	Health policy and coordination	Policy makers	High
Coaches	Other	Provide exercise and physical fitness support	Providers	High
Local Government Authorities	Public	Local coordination and policy support	Policy makers	High
Flemish Government	Public	Regional governance and healthcare policy	Policy makers	Medium
Professional Associations	Other	Representation of healthcare professionals	Providers	Medium
Buurtsport Antwerpen	Public	Sports promotion and physical activity in local communities	Providers	Medium
Local Service Centres (Buurtcentra)	Public	Community service centres providing local activities and services	Providers	Medium
Social Workers	Other	Support and referral of patients to healthcare services	Providers	Medium
Primary Care Zones in Antwerp (Eerstelijnszones)	Public	Coordination of primary care services in Antwerp	Program managers	Medium
Logo Antwerpen	Public/NGO	Local health promotion and education	Providers	Medium
General Practitioners (Huisartsen)	Private/Public	Provide primary healthcare and referrals	Providers	Medium
GP Circles (Huisartsenkringen)	Private/Public	Networks of general practitioners supporting patient referrals	Providers	Medium
Patient Associations	NGO/Other	Represent patient interests and provide advocacy	Patients, patient caregivers, patient advocates/ organizations	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Late intervention – Exercise on Prescription				
Local Spaces for Activities	Other	Provide venues for physical and social activities	Providers	Low
City of Antwerp Administration	Public	Health and sport management in the city	Program managers; Policy makers	Low
City's Political Officials (Schep en and Cabinet)	Public	Oversee policy decisions and local governance	Policy makers	Low
Cardiologists (Specialists)	Private	Provide specialist consultations for referred patients	Providers	Low
Domus Medica	Other	Offers e-learning resources for healthcare professionals	Providers	Low

The Stakeholder Map for Antwerp's 2nd late intervention is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Antwerp's 2nd stakeholders map.

ANTWERP - Exercise on Prescription

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Early intervention – Brave Move				
University of Antwerp	Public	Setting up living lab - research and analysis	-	High
HOWEST	Public	Setting up living lab - research and project management	-	High
Stad Antwerpen (municipality)	Public	Setting up living lab - project management and facilitation	-	High
KRAS	Civil society (youth organisation)	Youth partner involved in setting up living lab and overseeing group of teenagers	-	High
JES	Civil society (youth organisation)	Youth organisation active in neighbourhood	-	Low
SAAMO	Civil society (neighbourhood organisation)	Active in neighbourhood where living lab will take place	-	Medium
Girls in the city	NGO	Involved with theme of girls in public space	-	Medium
Elegast	Civil society (youth organisation)	Youth organisation	-	Low
Safe Space	NGO	Organisation working with young women	-	Low
District Antwerpen	Public	Responsible for activities within Antwerpen-Noord	-	Medium
District Borgerhout	Public	Responsible for activities within Borgerhout	-	Low
Endeavour	Private (architecture and urban planning organisation)	Involved with theme of girls in public space	-	Low
Permeke	Public library	Library working closely with youth in neighbourhood	-	Low
414 vzw	NGO	Active in living lab steering committee	-	Medium
Youth Unity Empowerment vzw	NGO	Active in living lab steering committee	-	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Antwerp Early intervention – Brave Move				
Entrakt	Private	Overseeing location of Stuivenbergziekenhuis (where living lab will take place)	-	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Bogota Late intervention – Ciclovía				
Secretaría Distrital de Movilidad (SDM)	public	Facilitator	Providers	High
Instituto Distrital de Recreación y Deporte (IDRD)	public	Organiser/Operator	Program managers	High
Guardía de la Ciclovía (GDC)	public	Operator	Providers; Logistics or support	High
Líder de Ruta (LDR)	public	Operator	Providers; Logistics or support	High
Concejo de Bogotá (CDB)	public	Facilitator/Funder	Policy makers	High
Empresa de Transporte de Carga (ETC)	public	Facilitator/Logistics	Providers; Logistics or support	High
Bogota Secretariat of Health (SDSB)	public	Ally/promotion	Providers	High
Bogota Metropolitan Police (PMB)	public	Facilitator/security/logistics	Providers; Logistics or support	High
Urban Development Institute (IDU)	public	Planner	Policy makers	High
Secretariat of Security	public	Facilitator/security	Providers; Logistics or support	Medium
Coexistence and Justice (SSCJ)	public	Facilitator/security/logistics	Providers; Logistics or support	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Bogota Late intervention - Ciclovía				
Ciclovía Authorized Vendors (VA)	private	Facilitator/ancillary services	Providers; Active community members and organizations	Medium
National Sports School (END)	private	Promotion	Product developers	Medium
Administrative Department for the Defense of Public Space (DADEP)	public	Facilitator/logistics	Providers; Logistics or support	Low
Institute for Social Economy (IPES)	public	Facilitator/ancillary services	Providers	Low
District Centre for Health Education and Research (CDEIS)	public	Research	Researchers	Low
Local Mayors (AL)	public	Facilitator	Policy makers	Low
Transmilenio (TM)	public	Ally	Logistics or support	Low
Secretariat of Government (SG)	public	Funder/facilitator	Providers	Low
Bicycle Collectives (SCO)	private	User groups	Active community members and organizations	Low
Recreation and Sports (SCRD)	public	Overseer/operator	Logistics or support	Low
Colombian Physical Activity Network (REDCOLAF)	private	User groups	Researchers; Active community members and organizations	Low

The Stakeholder Map for Bogota's late intervention is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Bogota's stakeholders map.

BOGOTA - Ciclovía

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Leve of involvement (high, medium, low)
Bogota				
Early intervention - Happiness Centres				
Concejo de Bogotá (CDB)	public	Funder/Facilitator	Policy makers	High
Alcaldía Mayor (AM)	public	Funder/facilitator	Policy makers	High
Instituto Distrital de Recreación y Deporte (IDRD)	public	Operator/organiser	Program managers	High
Secretaría de Cultura, Recreación y Deporte (SCRD)	public	Overseer	Program managers	High
organizaciones comunitarias (SCO)	civil society	Support/Users	Active community members and organizations	High
Alcaldía Local (AL)	public	Support	Policy makers	Medium
Juntas Administradoras Locales (JAL)	Civil society (neighbourhood organisation)	Facilitator	Policy makers	Medium
Usuarios	civil society	Users	Active community members and organizations; General public	Medium
Comunidad del Área de Influencia Directa (CAID)	civil society	Users	Active community members and organizations; General public	Medium
Líderes Formadores Deportivos (LFD)	civil society	Support/Users	Logistic or support; General public	Medium
Comando de Atención Inmediata (CAI)	public	Security/logistics	Logistic or support	Low
Colegios	public/private	Users	General public	Low
Centros Día (CD)	public/private	Users	General public	Low
Cajas de Compensación (CC)	Public	Ally/promotion	Logistics or support	Low
Artistas	private	Users	Active community members and organizations	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Bogota Early intervention - Happiness Centres				
Vendedores Ambulantes Informales (VAI)	private	Facilitator/ancillary services	Logistics or support	Low
Idearte	Public	Support	Logistics or support	Low
Escuelas, Clubes y Ligas Deportivas (ECLD)	civil society	Support / Users	Active community members and organizations; General public	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Kampala Early intervention - The Kampala Monthly Cycling Day				
Kampala Capital City Authority (KCCA)	Public (Government)	We hope to involve them as initiator in the Living Lab	Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	High
eBee Uganda	Private	Initiators	Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	Medium
ITDP	NGO	We hope to involve them as initiator in the Living Lab	Active community members and organisations; Researchers	High
WRI	NGO	Collaborators	Active community members and organisations; Researchers	medium
AirQo	Private	Collaborators	Researchers	Medium
Makerere University School of Public Health (MUSPH)	Academia	Initiators	Researchers	High
Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Private	Potential Funders	Potential Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	High
Cycling Advocacy Organizations	Private	Users	Active community members and organisations	Medium
Local Media Outlets (Newvision Newspapers)	Private	Initiators	Logistics or support	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Kampala Early intervention - The Kampala Monthly Cycling Day				
Cycling Event Management Companies	Private	Event Partners	Providers	Medium
Cyclists and Fitness Enthusiasts	Other	Users	General Public	Medium
Businesses Along the Cycling Route	Private	Potential beneficiaries	Logistics or support	Medium
Residents Along the Cycling Route	Other	Community members	General Public	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Kampala Late intervention - Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor				
KCCA	Public (Government)	Road Safety Engineer, KCCA	Policy makers	High
KCCA	Public (Government)	Director, Engineering and Technical Services	Policy makers	High
World Resources Institute (WRI)	NGO	Project Specialist, Cities Program World Resources Institute	Researchers	High
ITDP	NGO	Transport systems manager, ITDP	Researchers	High
eBee Africa	Private	Sustainable transport developer	Active community members and organizations	Medium
Uganda Police (Traffic)	Public (Government)	Commander KMP Traffic	Program manager	High
Ministry of Works and Transport	Public (Government)	Commissioner, Transport Regulation and Safety	Policy makers	High
Kampala City Traders Association (KACITA)	Private	Chairperson, business community	Providers	Medium
KCCA / Directorate of Engineering	Public (Government)	Deputy Director, Traffic and Transport Management	Policy makers	High

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Kampala Late intervention - Non-Motorized Transport (NMT) Pilot Corridor				
		Directorate of Engineering and Technical Services, KCCA		
KCCA / Directorate of Engineering and Technical Services / BIGRS	Public (Government)	Initiative Coordinator - Kampala Bloomberg Philanthropies Initiative for Global Road Safety (BIGRS)	Policy makers	High
National Physical Planning Board	Public (Government)	Chairperson, The National Physical Planning Board-Uganda	Policy makers	High
Boda Boda stage-Luwum street	Other	Chairperson of the Boda Boda stage-Luwum street	Providers	Medium
Jjemba Plaza Boda-boda stage member	Other	Member	Active community members and organisations	Low
Street vendor-Luwum street	Other	Vendor	Active community members and organisations	Low
Makerere University - TRIAD unit	Academia	Researcher	Researchers	Medium
Makerere University - TRIAD unit	Academia	Researcher	Researchers	Medium
CAMA	Academia	Assistant Lecturer, College of Engineering, Design, Art and Technology Makerere University	Researchers	Medium
Kaara-Africa	Private	Service provider	Providers	Low
Cyclist	Other	Cyclist	Active community members and organisations; General Public	Low

The Stakeholder Map for Kampala's late intervention is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Kampala's stakeholders map.

KAMPALA - Non Motorized Corridor

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Lima				
Late intervention - Program to lend facilities of the Villa María del Triunfo (VMT) Sports Complex to Schools.				
Special Legacy Project (PEL- from 2019 to 2025)	Public	<p>A triple role was identified: first, the institution is the promoter and financier of the intervention. Secondly, through the Integration and Promotion Unit of the PEL, they oversee the administration of the VMT Sports Complex and thus of the operational, execution and management activities of the intervention on a day-to-day basis.</p> <p>Finally, and thirdly, they provide medical assistance during the execution of the physical education classes, the Legacy provides specialized personnel for this function in case of any eventuality.</p>	Program Managers; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers; Providers	High
Instituto Peruano de Deporte (IPD; Peruvian Sport Institution)	Public	IPD will oversee 2019 Pan American Games facilities from 2025. The specific programs they will manage are not defined yet.	Program Managers; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers; Providers	High
Schools (public and private)	Public or private	Participating schools have a dual role. They are providers because they provide physical education teachers, and the students who attend classes fit under the category of “general public”, since they enjoy the benefits.	Providers ; General public	High
Municipality of VMT	Public	<p>They oversee the sustainable development of the VMT district, through the provision of services, participatory, efficient, and transparent management.</p> <p>Two key areas have been identified: The Local Development Management (GDELDC)</p>	Policy makers	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Lima				
Late intervention - Program to lend facilities of the Villa María del Triunfo (VMT) Sports Complex to Schools.				
		who provides the authorization for the operation of the PEL, and the Sport Management, who is in charge of promoting interventions with a focus on improving public health in the district.		
Jose Carlos Mariategui Police Station	Public	They have the role of providing security in the intervention zone and have also identified themselves as spokespersons for the community.	Logistics or support	Low
UE	Other	The European Union is funding the CITYMOVE project that will evaluate the intervention in question.	Payers of funders of research	Medium
Ministry of Transportation and Communications (MTC)	Public	The Legacy is an entity attached to the Ministry of Transportation and Communications (MTC), therefore the approval of any regulatory document or action to be executed by the Legacy is subject to the signature and approval of the MTC.	Policy makers	Low
MINEDU (Ministry of Education)	Public	The Ministry of Education (MINEDU) is the governing body that enacts the General Education Law and the National Basic Education Curriculum, and all schools nationwide must abide by its indications and guidelines.	Policy makers	Low
CITY MOVE	Other	Through UNALM (partner Lima) and a team of 3 professionals: a senior researcher and two junior researchers and master thesis students. They will carry out activities in the framework of the CITYMOVE project to evaluate the intervention.	Researchers	Medium

The Stakeholder Map for Lima's late intervention is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Lima's stakeholder map.

LIMA

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Lima Early intervention - Independencia Greenbelt				
Municipality of Independencia- Human and Social Development Office	Public	Currently, there is no direct link with the intervention in the Greenbelt of Independencia; however, their participation is essential, as they promote education, health, sports, and recreation programs aimed at improving the quality of life for children, older adults, women, people with disabilities, and the general community in the district. Some of these initiatives could be implemented in the Greenbelt.	Program managers	Low
Municipality of Independencia- Environment Office	Public	Responsible for the administration and management of the Greenbelt.	Program managers	High
Municipality of Independencia- Community participation Office	Public	Facilitates communication with the population of the district of Independencia.	Logistics or support	Low
Community associations and grassroots organizations	civil society	They are beneficiaries of the intervention and play an active role in the development and maintenance of the Greenbelt.	Active community members and organizations	High
Ciudad Viva	NGO (Non-Governmental Organization)	They supported the development of the Greenbelt and can collaborate in specific activities.	Active community members and organizations	Low
PreDES	NGO (Non-Governmental Organization)	They supported the development of the Greenbelt and can collaborate in specific activities.	Active community members and organizations	Low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Ljubljana Late intervention - Walk along the wire				
Health Section of Municipality of Ljubljana	public	Program manager	Program managers	medium
City municipality of Ljubljana - Section for sports programs	public	Program manager	Program managers	high
City municipality of Ljubljana - Department of Health and Social Welfare	public	Program manager	Program managers	high
City municipality of Ljubljana - Department for development and infrastructure in the field of sports	public	Program manager	Program managers	medium
Association for the execution of sports programs - TIMING Ljubljana	public	Organiser	Program managers	high
National Institute for Public Health	public	Tracking and monitoring	Program managers	low
CHCL Sports Association	public	Promotion	Logistics or support	medium
Slovenian Olympic Committee	NGO	Promotion	Logistics or support	low
Sport Ljubljana	public	Program manager	Program managers	high
Ministry of Health	public	Tracking and monitoring	Program managers	low
Ministry of Economy, Tourism and Sports	public	Tracking and monitoring	Program managers	medium
Public bus company Ljubljana LPP d.o.o.	public	Organiser	Program managers	medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Ljubljana Late intervention - Walk along the wire				
Association of principals and assistant principals of primary schools	private society	Promotion	Logistic or support	medium
Association of principals (of high schools)	private society	Promotion	Logistic or support	medium
The association of kindergarten principals of Slovenia	private society	Promotion	Logistic or support	high
Sports Association of Ljubljana	public	Promotion	Logistic or support	medium

The Stakeholder Map for Ljubljana’s late intervention is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Ljubljana's stakeholders map.

LJUBLJANA - Walk along the Wire

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Rotterdam Late intervention - De Groene Overschiese				
Municipality Rotterdam (Societal Development)	Public	Fund intervention, involved in initiating, implementation and sustaining phase on a strategic level. Links map to healthcare providers, implementation and sustaining phase on a hands-on level	Program Managers; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	high
Municipality Rotterdam (City Development)	Public	Initiator, monitor implementation and sustaining phase on a strategic level. Link to the walking programme of the City, involved in initiating, implementation, and sustaining phase on a strategic level.	Policy makers; Program managers	high
Municipality Rotterdam (neighbourhood manager)	Public	Initiator, hands-on involvement in neighbourhood during initiating, implementation and sustaining phase.	Program Managers; Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers; Policy makers; Program managers	high
Initiating initiatives on the map	Public	Organise activities at their organisation to stimulate health/social, highly involved in implementation phase and sustaining phase of De Groene Overschiese, so not only their own organisation.	Active community members and organizations	High
WMO Radar (social welfare organization)	Public	Initiator and implementation-phase, link to the walking groups and are the first point for referred patients from GPs to get in touch with.	Providers	Medium
General practitioners (GP)	Public	One GP was initiator and highly involved at the beginning, now the GPs are involved in the implementation and sustaining phase, by having maps in their waiting rooms and can refer their patients to walk/cycle De	Providers	At first high (GP initiator), now low

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Rotterdam Late intervention - De Groene Overschiese				
		Groene Overschiese or join one of the walking clubs.		
Neighbourhood GP association	Public	Are the link between municipality and GPs, help the municipality to scale the amount of GPs who have maps/refer to De Groene Overschiese	Providers	Medium
Participating initiatives on the map	Public	Organise activities at their organisation to stimulate health/social, more focused on their own activities than on the whole De Groene Overschiese but are involved in the implementation and sustaining phase.	Active community members and organizations	Medium
KrachtGroen	Private	Active community member from other route that helped develop, implement and sustain the intervention	Active community member and organizations	High
Residents	-	Participate in the intervention after implementation	General public	Low
Other healthcare delivery organisations in the neighbourhood (e.g. Rotterdam physiotherapy)	Public	The Societal Development Municipality officer is working with some other healthcare organisations to also start referring to De Groene Overschiese, involved in sustaining phase.	Providers	Low
Other organisations in the neighbourhood (e.g. neighbourhood newspaper)	Public/private	Some other neighbourhood organisations are involved in promoting De Groene Overschiese through their channels, involved in implementing and sustaining phase.	Active community members and organizations; General public	Low
Walking groups	Public	The walking groups are organised by both WMO Radar (see above) but also other	Patients, patient caregivers, patient advocates/ organizations	Medium

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Rotterdam Late intervention - De Groene Overschie				
		organisations/individuals, they are important to the sustaining phase because they give people access to De Groene Overschie in a group-setting.		
Map and activity card designer	Public	The designer is involved in the implementation phase and updates the map and designs the bi-annual activity cards	Product developer	Low
Municipality (City Management, implementation branch)	Public	This part of the municipality is involved in practical city management, e.g. improving sidewalks. If participants of De Groene Overschie have a complaint about part of the route, this is adjusted faster because the area is part of De Groene Overschie	Product developer	Low
Municipality Rotterdam (neighbourhood networker)	Public	There is a new neighbourhood networker in Overschie, unclear yet what role they will play, in sustaining phase.	Program managers	Low (hope to move to medium/high)

The Stakeholder Map for Ljubljana's late intervention is shown in Figure 8Figure 7.

Figure 8. Rotterdam's stakeholders map.

ROTTERDAM - Groene Overschiese

Stakeholder	5. Type of institution	6. Role in the intervention	Category of stakeholder according CITY MOVE	7. Level of involvement (high, medium, low)
Rotterdam Early intervention - In the neighbourhood of Tarwewijk				
Municipality Rotterdam (Societal Development)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Municipality Rotterdam (City Management)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Municipality Rotterdam (neighbourhood manager)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Tarwekracht (neighbourhood organisation)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
WMO Radar (social welfare organization)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
GPs	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Neighbourhood GP organisation	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Neighbourhood organisations/green initiatives	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
KrachtGroen	Private	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Residents	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Other healthcare delivery organisations in the neighbourhood (e.g. physiotherapy)	Public	We hope to involve them as initiator in the ULL	-	N/A
Engineering/urban planning company	Private	Not sure yet	-	N/A
Researchers from Erasmus University Rotterdam/Schools of Applied Science	Public	Initiators	-	medium (we hope)

3. CORE CONTEXT ELEMENTS

GAPPA relates physical activity directly to the 2030 Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs) 3 (good health and well-being), whilst indirectly contributing to others (SDG2, ending all forms of malnutrition; SDG4, quality education; SDG5, gender equality; SDG8, decent work and economic growth; SDG9, industry, innovation and infrastructure; SDG10, reduced inequalities; SDG11, sustainable cities and communities; SDG12, responsible production and consumption; SDG13, climate action; SDG15, life on land; SDG16, peace, justice and strong institutions; and SDG17, partnerships) recognizing there are multiple policies that can be implemented to promote PA in urban environments (GAPPA, 2018).

In CITY-MOVE, each intervention, from each city, might follow a particular route to a more active society, environment, people and system. The **Core context elements** is an activity that proposes researchers step back in time to understand the intervention through a multi-spectral lens by knowing the conditions that prompted or motivated the design and development, delivery and evolution of the intervention. The conditions reflect different factors and configurations of context elements, they can be social, cultural, geographical, political, and economic. Information has been collected from publicly accessible records and documents and during interviews using tool 1.2. It is important to acknowledge that the context is dynamic and will inevitably change over time. Therefore, CITY-MOVE contact points have also been asked to describe relevant changes in the context or, for instance, how the intervention can change the context itself.

Task 1.3 is also related to the activities from other work packages in CITY- MOVE. The Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) was applied to the late interventions as part of WP3. The TIDieR is a guide reporting checklist developed to improve the completeness of reporting, and ultimately the replicability, of interventions on health (Hoffmann et al., 2014). The purpose of identifying core context elements in late interventions is to comprehend the drivers and the complexity that might create barriers or opportunities to change. Early interventions will be developed in CITY-MOVE as Living-labs through co-creation (WP2). To frame the problem effectively and to present a collective solution, researchers will need to understand the context and how it relates to the stakeholders. A first evaluation will be made during year 1 of CITY-MOVE, and a second during year 4, in order to document, validate and compare the core context elements within and between each intervention. A Multi- criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) will be also conducted (WP5), where one of the inputs is the core context elements mapped, especially for the early interventions.

3.1 TOOLS AND METHODS FOR COLLECTING DATA

With the inputs from all the WPs, received during the Bogotá meeting (May, 2024), WP1 researchers defined a list of elements to help city researchers in understanding their interventions. The list was not static and the items within each element could be skipped or augmented, depending on the specifics of the intervention. A template table was provided to facilitate information gathering and reporting. Columns were divided into: Element (broad categories e.g. Culture); type of element (specific category in Element e.g. religious norms); level of relevance (1- little relevance; 2- relevant; 3- very relevant); and explanation about the level of relevance of each core context element mentioned. To enrich the information provided, researchers identified key uncertainties that are relevant for the implementation of the intervention.

To facilitate the collecting and reporting of the information, three guiding questions were provided:

- A. What are the conditions that lead or motivated the design and development, delivery and evolution of the intervention?
- B. Which can be considered relevant changes in context OR how the intervention can change the context itself?
- C. Which are the key uncertainties that are relevant for the implementation of the intervention?

For governance, it was suggested that researchers provide an organigram that clearly expressed the multilevel organizational system related to each specific intervention case in CITY-MOVE.

In addition to the Core context elements table, a SWOT analysis session was conducted with the stakeholders from the late intervention. SWOT stands for: **S**trengths, **W**eakness, **O**pportunities, **T**hreats. The SWOT method was originally developed for business and industry, but it is equally useful in community health and development work. A SWOT analysis was used to assist researchers in guiding the stakeholders to identify the internal strengths and weaknesses (S-W) of their intervention activities, as well as broader, external opportunities and threats (O-T) that impact the current or future delivery of the intervention. Developing a fuller awareness of the interventions will help the stakeholders make decisions about immediate and future activities.

3.2 RESULTS

With the inputs provided by each CITY-MOVE contact point, it was possible to secure a very good overview of Core context elements, summarized in Table 3. The five most mentioned elements are respectively: Socioeconomic (54), Environment (52), Security (42), Political (39) and Infrastructure (38). An analysis relating the type of element with its level of relevance will be lately done in order to attest which of them have more or less impact in CITY-MOVE intervention, additionally, the analysis will reveal the similarities between cases.

Table 3: CITY-MOVE Core Context Elements Summary

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
23	City characteristics	Population density	3	Borgerhout and Antwerpen Noord are densely populated, less green and open public space, which can limit opportunities for physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
24	City characteristics	Topography	2	Antwerp's flat terrain makes it easier for activities like cycling and running, promoting physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
38	Culture	Religious norms	2	Religious norms may mean girls less likely to do exercise	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
39	Culture	Cultural norms	3	Cultural norms may mean girls less likely to do exercise	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
40	Culture	Migration	2	High proportion of people in these neighbourhoods have a migration background, can influence social dynamics and accessibility to services.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
65	Environment	Man made hazards	2	Air and water pollution can deter populations engaging in exercise in Antwerp.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
66	Environment	Natural hazards	2	Risks of flooding or heatwaves can limit safe opportunities for outdoor physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
67	Environment	Specific environmental indicators on air, soil and water quality	3	Poor air and water quality can significantly deter outdoor physical activities and pose health risks.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
68	Environment	Extreme weather	2	Heatwaves and the urban heat island effect in Antwerp during the summer can reduce the likelihood of engaging in physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
69	Environment	Noise pollution	2	High levels of noise pollution can be off-putting for exercising outdoors.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
70	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	3	Accessibility to safe and clean environments is crucial for encouraging physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
71	Environment	Biodiversity	2	Greater biodiversity in urban spaces can have a positive impact on mental health and encourage outdoor activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
72	Environment	Clean streets	2	Clean public spaces enhance the attractiveness of outdoor areas for exercise.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
109	Governance	Relationships between departments	2	Collaboration between different government departments can enhance the effectiveness of public health initiatives, including those promoting physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
142	Infrastructure	Transportation network	3	A well-connected transportation network facilitates access to places where physical activities can be performed.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
143	Infrastructure	Utilities	3	Availability of utilities such as water and toilets in public areas supports longer and more comfortable engagement in outdoor activities	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
144	Infrastructure	Sportive facilities	3	Availability and accessibility of sports facilities are crucial for promoting regular physical activity among youth.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
145	Infrastructure	Quality of infrastructure	3	High-quality infrastructure encourages more people to engage in physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
146	Infrastructure	Accessibility and connectivity	3	Good connectivity and accessibility of public spaces are essential for ensuring everyone, including teenage girls, can participate in physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
147	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	3	Welcoming and well-maintained public spaces encourage more physical activity and social interaction.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
168	Political	Budget cuts	3	Less money available for Youth services at City of Antwerp, for example, disproportionately impacts girls	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
169	Political	Political agenda	3	The ideology of political parties in charge determines policy and prioritization of public health and youth services.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
170	Political	Population trust	2	Population trust in government affects the success of public interventions, including those aimed at increasing physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
171	Political	Informality-formality	1	Informality in political processes can affect physical activity initiatives by impacting on funding, policy enforcement, trust and fragmentation.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
172	Political	Ideology	2	Ideological stances of the ruling parties can influence policies related to public space and inclusivity, affecting physical activity opportunities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
226	Safety	Perceptions about safety	3	Perceptions of streets being unsafe limiting teenage girls' physical activity	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
227	Security	Personal or property crime	3	High crime rates deter individuals from using public spaces for physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
228	Security	No proper safe walkways	3	Lack of safe walkways discourages walking and other forms of outdoor exercise.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
229	Security	Car accidents	3	High rates of traffic accidents can deter cycling and walking.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
230	Security	Adequate road signage	2	Proper signage enhances safety and encourages the use of public spaces for exercise.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
231	Security	Lighting	2	Adequate lighting in public spaces improves safety and encourages physical activity during early morning or evening hours.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
232	Security	Police presence	2	Visible police presence can enhance feeling of safety for some groups but may also create discomfort for others (e.g. undocumented migrants).	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
25	Socioeconomic	Equality	2	Teenage girls with disabilities face additional barriers to moving around the city.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
245	Socioeconomic	Demographics	3	It is important to understand for G.I.R.L as it focuses on teenage girls and looks at categories within this.	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
246	Socioeconomic	Education level	1	Education level can relate to understanding of importance of physical activity for health	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
247	Socioeconomic	Income	3	Income has a substantial impact on health factors and access to exercise and resources	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
248	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	2	Social cohesion between different groups reduces discrimination and fear of using public spaces	Antwerp	Belgium	Brave-Move	Early
26	City Characteristics	Population density	3	High population density increases the need for accessible public spaces and facilities for physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
27	City Characteristics	Topography	1	Antwerp's flat urban landscape provides easy access for outdoor activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
41	Culture	Migration	2	Migrants can face language barriers which can influence participation.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
73	Environment	Air quality	2	Poor environmental conditions like bad air quality discourage outdoor physical activity.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
74	Environment	Extreme weather	1	Extreme weather, such as heatwaves, may reduce outdoor physical activity, necessitating indoor alternatives.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
110	Governance	Level of government and power on decision	3	Local government support and coordination within the health system are crucial for effective implementation.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
123	Health	Health status & Access to services	3	Chronic conditions (e.g., NCDs) and access to healthcare are key factors in referral and program success.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
148	Infrastructure	Infrastructure (transport, utilities)	3	Reliable public transport, safe sidewalks, and well-maintained public spaces are essential for access.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
149	Infrastructure	Sports facilities & public spaces	3	Accessible, well-maintained sports facilities and public spaces encourage physical activity and engagement.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
173	Political	Political support & funding	3	Political backing and funding are crucial for the program's sustainability and reach.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
174	Political	Population trust	2	Trust in public institutions affects participation in government-endorsed health programs like this one.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
224	Safety	Perceptions about safety	2	Perceptions of safety, crime rates, and adequate lighting around public spaces are key to encouraging participation in physical activities.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
247	Socioeconomic	Income	3	Income has a substantial impact on health factors and access to exercise and resources	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on prescription	Late
249	Socioeconomic	Demographics	3	Programming must account for diverse needs of age groups, people with disabilities, and socioeconomic status.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
250	Socioeconomic	Education level	3	Lower education impact health literacy and access to services, requiring tailored interventions.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
251	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	2	Strong community ties can encourage participation in physical activity and group exercise programs.	Antwerp	Belgium	Exercise on Prescription	Late
28	City characteristics	Population density	2	Higher population density increases demand for services, requiring better resource planning.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
42	Culture	Cultural norms	2	Cultural and religious attitudes can shape health behaviours and influence kiosk use in a diverse population.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
43	Culture	Migration	3	Migrants can have increased distrust, affecting their access to health services.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
75	Environment	General environmental condition	2	Poor environmental conditions increase health issues, driving more people to the kiosk for care.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
76	Environment	Extreme weather	2	Heatwaves and extreme weather may reduce access to the kiosk, especially for vulnerable populations.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
111	Governance	Level of government and power on decision	3	Local government involvement can affect funding, service range, and long-term sustainability.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
112	Governance	Organizational structure of the health system at different levels	2	Coordination between health services and the kiosk is crucial for continuity of care and effective referrals.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
113	Governance	Relationships between departments	2	Cooperation between health, social, and housing departments can improve the kiosk's ability to address social determinants of health.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
150	Infrastructure	Infrastructure (transport, utilities, signage)	3	Good public transport, reliable utilities, and traffic safety are essential for accessibility to the health kiosk.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
151	Infrastructure	Public spaces & welcoming areas	3	Clean, well-maintained, and welcoming spaces around the kiosk enhance user experience and attract visitors.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
175	Political	Political support & funding	3	Political backing (including planning permissions) and sufficient funding are critical for kiosk sustainability and service offerings.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
176	Political	Population trust	3	Trust in public institutions impacts on the willingness of people to use the kiosk for preventive care.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
177	Political	Ideology	3	Political ideologies shape health policy and funding priorities, influencing kiosk operations.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
225	Safety	Perceptions about safety	3	Perceptions of safety, crime rates, and lighting near the kiosk are key to encouraging usage, especially for women and the elderly.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
252	Socioeconomic	Demographics	3	The kiosk has to consider the demographics it serves, as there are a high percentage of elderly, migrants, and people with disabilities, to ensure health services are tailored to their needs.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
253	Socioeconomic	Income	3	Lower education impacts health literacy, and lower income limits access, requiring targeted interventions.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
254	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	2	Strong community connections improve trust and encourage kiosk use.	Antwerp	Belgium	Health Kiosk	Late
15	City characteristics	Population density	3	Bogotá is a dense city (13,500 per sq. Km - Secretary of Planning). Happiness Centres (HC) are located in densely populated areas with respect to the rest of the city except for HC Cometas which is situated on top of a hill. Accessibility for all is easy on foot or public transportation.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
16	City characteristics	City extension	2	The city a large metropolitan area, HC are planned to impact on surrounding population, users are not expected to come from long distances.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
17	City characteristics	Geography	3	At 2,600 m.a.s.l., the temperature tends to remain between 8 and 20 degrees C. This does not affect attendance to HC. There are 2 rainy seasons in the year March/April - Sept/Nov, rains can be copious and last for long periods, this may affect attendance to HCs.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
18	City characteristics	Land use/land cover	3	4 HCs are in mainly residential areas whereas one is in a mainly commercial area (Chapinero), this may affect number and characteristics of users. They are also located in less polluted areas; this may increase user attendance.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
44	Culture	Religious norms	2	Catholics makeup most of the population. Church services and ceremonies take place on Sundays. It is not clear how this may affect use of HC	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
45	Culture	Cultural norms	2	Different age groups do not mix with each other and have different PA activities (skating for the young, walking for the old). This is also true for some economically differentiated groups, ethnicity may not be much of an issue. Some indigenous groups temporarily stationed in the city probably will not be accessing the HC.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
46	Culture	Migration	2	New migrants may not take part on PA activities at HC, there are discrimination issues, segregation and the population may not be yet established in a permanent dwelling.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
47	Culture	Identity	2	Overweight or obese populations may not access the HC for PA for fear of stigma or low self-esteem.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
77	Environment	Seismic	3	Seismic activity is not uncommon in Bogotá (a mountain seismic region) however this is not likely to affect attendance to HC. These structures (buildings) have been constructed within seismic regulations.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
78	Environment	Natural hazards	3	As far as we know floods, earthquakes, lightning and other natural hazards are not likely to affect the regular use of HCs.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
79	Environment	Specific environmental indicators on air, soil and water quality	3	Drinking water availability has recently become a problem for the city, currently (2025) there is rationing of drinking water provision for every locality of the city every 9 days for 24 hours. This has most likely affected HC attendance in the days when the rationing takes place.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
81	Environment	Light pollution	2	HCs are mainly open for users during daylight hours (6 am to 6 pm or even shorter periods depending on the day of the week).	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
82	Environment	Biodiversity	3	Some HCs take advantage of the surrounding park areas with varying degrees of tree and vegetation coverage (Fontanar and Tunal have relatively little tree coverage while Cometas is surrounded by a forested area).	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
83	Environment	Clean streets	3	People are allowed to use HC after registering in a database, signage on proper use of installations and sanitation are displayed throughout the buildings, HC personnel educate users on proper use and care of equipment.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
114	Governance	Organizational structure of the health system at different levels	3	It defines the distribution of responsibilities and the capacity to respond to the needs of the population.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
115	Governance	Organizational structure of the health system at different levels	3	It determines the coordination between the different actors and the efficiency in the provision of services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
116	Governance	Relationships between departments	2	Coordination between government departments is important to address complex problems such as public health.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
124	Health	People's health status	3	Overall health of population can affect the use of HC. It is unknown if HC influences people's health.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
125	Health	Health facilities	2	Access to quality healthcare in areas of influence of HC may affect attendance to HC. Local physician/nurse prescription of PA can be implemented at the HC.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
126	Health	Nutrition	3	The sale of healthy foods within or around CEFs can help complement healthy lifestyle habits in parallel (PA)	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
127	Health	People with disabilities	3	Socially excluded groups and people with disabilities may not be able to equally use HC, because of lack of access to transportation means although HC facilities have been constructed and are able to cater to people with disabilities.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
128	Health	Mortality rate	3	Impact on the decrease of mortality rates in the population.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
152	Infrastructure	Transportation network	3	Transportation of users to and from HCs is affected by transport infrastructure and availability. Users in the immediate vicinity reach HC by foot but some may need to use transport, this population may be affected by this.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
153	Infrastructure	Utilities	3	Drinking water availability is important for use of HC facilities, neighbourhood safety may affect attendance to the centre, street illumination at night may also affect attendance by women for example.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
154	Infrastructure	Sports facilities	3	Other sports facilities available close by may compete with HC	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
155	Infrastructure	Quality of infrastructure (roads)	3	Use of quality public space for physical activity.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
156	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	3	Coordination liaison for the realization of physical activity outside the proposed route with the use of parks and gardens, among others.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
181	Political	Different political backgrounds	2	Importance given to HC by the politician in power affects dedicated budget	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
182	Political	Political agenda	3	Priority given to different programs in the City will affect HC	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
183	Political	Corruption	3	It weakens trust in institutions and affects efficiency in the provision of public services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
184	Political	Population trust	3	Fundamental to government legitimacy and citizen participation.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
185	Political	Informality-Formality	2	It influences employment generation, tax collection and quality of services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
186	Political	Ideology	2	It guides the visions and proposals of the different political actors, influencing decision making.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
203	Security	Civil unrest	2	Occurrence of gatherings and localized protests could affect access to HC	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
204	Security	Personal or property crimes	3	Adjacent roads and access perception of security to and from HC will affect number of people that use HC, women and children may be differentially affected	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
205	Security	Crime rate	3	Adjacent roads and access perception of security to and from HC will affect number of people that use HC, women and children may be differentially affected	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
206	Security	Car accidents	2	Presence or absence of curbs or adequate conditions for these may hinder access of to and from HC	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
207	Security	Adequate road signs	3	Fundamental to prevent accidents and ensure the flow of traffic.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
208	Security	Police presence	3	It influences the perception of security and the capacity to respond to emergency situations.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
209	Security	Public systems without guard	2	The vulnerability of these systems to acts of crime affects the provision of public services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
210	Security	Lighting	2	Adequate public lighting reduces insecurity and makes it more difficult to commit crimes.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
233	Security	Perceptions about safety	3	Reduction of dangers to citizens through the cooperation of authorities and territorial entities for the use of public space.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
255	Socioeconomic	Demographics	3	Composition of the general population determines its ability to take advantage of PA interventions	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
256	Socioeconomic	Number of people living in urban areas	2	How many people live in the surrounding area of each Happiness Centre, the potential impact of the intervention	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
257	Socioeconomic	Human development indicators	3	May affect the capacity of potential users to actually use the facilities	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
258	Socioeconomic	Number of people with access to sanitation	2	Access to sanitation is a good indicator of human development and capacity to attend these CEFE	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
259	Socioeconomic	Population growth rate	2	Internal migration and organic growth will affect the number of people that use the facilities	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
260	Socioeconomic	Income distribution population	3	Population in Bogotá varies greatly socioeconomically speaking, these differences may affect attendance or access of the community to the centres	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
261	Socioeconomic	Educational level	2	Identifies the specific needs of the population and designs strategies to ensure inclusion and well-being.	Bogotá	Colombia	Happiness Centres	Early
19	City characteristics	Population density	3	Bogotá is a dense city (13,500 per sq. Km - Secretary of Planning). There are 127 Km of Ciclovía covering most of the city. Accessibility for all is easy on foot or by public transportation for most users.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
20	City characteristics	City extension	2	Bogotá is a large and segregated city. Poor areas are in the outskirts, particularly to the south, SE and SW. Northern areas are richer although many poor areas are adjacent to richer ones. Ciclovía is extensive but it's limited to larger roads. Only small roads reach the outskirts and poorer neighbourhoods; this probably restricts access differentially among city groups.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
21	City characteristics	Geography	3	Climate: There are 2 rainy seasons (explained above), attendance to Ciclovía when raining is far lower than with fair weather or with sunny days.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
22	City characteristics	Land use/land cover	3	Air pollution levels remain safe most of the year so this is an unlikely factor on the use of Ciclovía by the community. Ciclovía is located mostly in residential and commercial areas. Some industrial areas near Ciclovía are closed on Sundays, this is not likely to affect its use.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
48	Culture	Religious norms	2	Church goes on Sundays (vast majority of the population) can affect number of users and PA time during Ciclovía.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
50	Culture	Migration	2	Migrants may not take part on PA activities at Ciclovía, there are discrimination issues, segregation and the population may not be yet established in a permanent dwelling.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
51	Culture	Identity	2	Overweight or obese populations may not access Ciclovía for PA for fear of stigma or low self-esteem.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
88	Culture	Identity	2	Ciclovía is mainly open for users during daylight hours (7 am to 2 pm). Once or twice a year there is nocturnal Ciclovía where streets are closed between 6 pm and 12 am. This is mostly during the Christmas shopping season.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
85	Environment	Natural hazards	3	During the rainy season, less people use the Ciclovía, in addition localized flooding and lightning may take place affecting number of people using th Ciclovía and time of use.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
86	Environment	Specific environmental indicators on air, soil and water quality	3	Drinking water availability has recently become a problem for the city, currently (2025) there is rationing of drinking water provision for every locality of the city every 9 days for 24 hours. This has most likely affected Ciclovía attendance among users subject to rationing when on Sunday takes place.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
89	Environment	Biodiversity	3	Bogotá has varying tree coverage depending on the street, this is not likely an issue with the Ciclovía users	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
90	Environment	Clean streets	3	Guardians of Ciclovía have a role in user education and citizen culture promotion, this has enhanced proper behaviour within the Ciclovía.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
117	Governance	Level of government and power on decision	3	Ciclovía ultimately depends on political will and budget allocation from the higher local government (Mayor and City council). Ciclovía is highly appreciated by the users and the community, and no politician has tried to stop it, but this is always a possibility.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
118	Governance	Organizational structure of the health system at different levels	3	It determines the coordination between the different actors and the efficiency in the provision of services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
119	Governance	Relationships between departments	2	Coordination between government departments is important to address complex problems such as public health.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
129	Health	People's health status	3	There have been many studies evaluating the health benefits of Ciclovía on health improvement.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
130	Health	Health facilities	2	Healthcare facilities are unevenly distributed throughout the city, the northern part has proportionally more healthcare facilities than the southern part of the city. The health secretary has several health posts evenly distributed in the Ciclovía. Urgent care can be swiftly provided to users in need and transportation to a healthcare facility may influence the outcome.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
131	Health	Nutrition	3	Food insecurity is prevalent in lower tiers of society; low-income housing is usually located far from Ciclovía.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
132	Health	People with disabilities	3	There has been evidence of differential access to Ciclovía of poor areas and far out areas of the city. Access of people with disabilities has not been suited to our knowledge.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
133	Health	Mortality rate	3	Impact on the decrease of mortality rates in the population.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
157	Infrastructure	Transportation network	3	City mobility is significantly altered during the Ciclovía, it is usually not very traumatic since Sunday traffic is low. Some users use public transport to get to and from Ciclovía. They may be affected.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
158	Infrastructure	Utilities	3	Users living in areas where there is water rationing on Sunday may opt not to go to Ciclovía for example. Traffic and safety are well managed during Ciclovía but this is logistically complex and requires a fair amount of coordination between the operator and collaborating institutions.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
159	Infrastructure	Sports facilities	3	Within Ciclovía several fixed spaces are used for additional PA activities (Recreovía) for example that are specially valued by groups of users (women and children).	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
160	Infrastructure	Quality of infrastructure (roads)	3	Use of quality public space for physical activity.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
161	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	3	Coordination liaison for the realization of physical activity outside the proposed route with the use of parks and gardens, among others.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
187	Political	Different political backgrounds	2	Importance given to Ciclovía by the politician in power affects dedicated budget	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
188	Political	Political agenda	3	Priority given to different programs in the city will affect Ciclovía	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
189	Political	Corruption	3	It weakens trust in institutions and affects efficiency in the provision of public services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
190	Political	Population trust	3	Fundamental to government legitimacy and citizen participation.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
191	Political	Informality-Formality	2	It influences employment generation, tax collection and quality of services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
192	Political	Ideology	2	It guides the visions and proposals of the different political actors, influencing decision making.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
211	Security	Civil unrest	2	Occurrence of gatherings and localized protests could affect access to Ciclovia or even its occurrence on a given date	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
212	Security	Personal or property crimes	3	Perception of security within Ciclovia encourages people (families and children) to use it. Getting to and from Ciclovia is also affected by perception of security.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
213	Security	Crime rate	3	Adjacent roads and access perception of security to and from HC will affect number of people that use HC, women and children may be differentially affected	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
214	Security	Car accidents	2	Adequate road closure to cars is key for users. In some areas, cars occasionally invade or must make use of a closed street, increasing the risk of accidents.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
215	Security	Adequate road signs	3	Fundamental to prevent accidents and ensure the flow of traffic.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
216	Security	Police presence	3	It influences the perception of security and the capacity to respond to emergency situations.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
217	Security	Public systems without guard	2	The vulnerability of these systems to acts of crime affects the provision of public services.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
218	Security	Lighting	2	Adequate public lighting reduces insecurity and makes it more difficult to commit crimes.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
234	Security	Perceptions about safety	3	Reduction of dangers to citizens through the cooperation of authorities and territorial entities for the use of public space.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late
262	Socioeconomic	Demographics	3	Affects the composition of user population	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovia	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
263	Socioeconomic	Number of people living in urban areas	2	How many people live in nearby neighbourhoods, potential impact of the intervention.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
264	Socioeconomic	Human development indicators	3	May affect the capacity of potential users to use the facilities	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
265	Socioeconomic	Number of people with access to sanitation	2	Access to sanitation is a good indicator of human development and capacity to attend Ciclovía	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
266	Socioeconomic	Population growth rate	2	Internal migration and organic growth will affect number of people that use Ciclovía	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
267	Socioeconomic	Income distribution population	3	Population in Bogotá varies greatly socioeconomically speaking, these differences may affect attendance or access of the community to the centres	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
268	Socioeconomic	Educational level	2	Identifies the specific needs of the population and designs strategies to ensure inclusion and well-being.	Bogotá	Colombia	Ciclovía	Late
1	Culture	Cultural norms	2	Culture has a large influence on the uptake of cycling for females in Uganda. Many women in the 1990s and early 2000s were not encouraged to cycle in central Uganda, thereby it was viewed as an act of rebellion for a woman to cycle. This is changing slowly over time.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
91	Environment	Clean streets	2	Clean streets enhance the event's atmosphere and attract participation, making it moderately relevant for creating a pleasant experience	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
324	Culture	Religious norms	2	Religious norms have a minimal impact on the cycling event, as this is largely a secular activity focused on urban mobility and health rather than religious influence.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
92	Environment	Weather conditions	3	Weather conditions significantly impact the comfort and safety of cycling events, as adverse weather such as heavy rains could deter participants or cause safety issues.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
3	Infrastructure	Quality of infrastructure	3	Good infrastructure, including smooth roads and dedicated lanes, is essential for cyclists' safety and comfort, making it very relevant to the event's success. Infrastructure quality is important for cycling whereby if the roads are poorly constructed, with potholes and poor drainage as is the case on many roads in Kampala, cycling on such roads is harder and risky. This can deter participants from attending the event.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
4	Infrastructure	Accessibility and connectivity	3	Accessibility and connectivity of the cycling routes are very relevant as they ensure inclusivity and convenience for all participants, encouraging greater attendance	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
178	Political	Different political background	1	Political diversity has minimal direct impact on the event; while diverse views exist, the initiative is largely community-driven with support from even non-Ugandan leaders across Africa and the globe.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
179	Political	Corruption	2	Cycling events in Kampala align with KCCA's agenda to promote sustainable urban mobility, making it highly relevant as it boosts alignment and support from city authorities to make Kampala a smart city. Corruption can impact infrastructure funding and trust in initiatives, moderately affecting the event's support and infrastructure reliability.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
236	Security	Lighting	3	Adequate lighting is important for visibility and safety during the event but is moderately relevant as the event is held during daylight hours. However, since the overall goal of the event is to advocate for safe cycling, Lighting is an important element so that cyclists can safely cycle even late in the evenings/night when coming back from work, and, or for physical activity/leisure.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
237	Security	Road safety	3	Road safety is extremely relevant as it directly impacts on the well-being of participants and the overall success of the Kampala Cycling Day. Ensuring safe cycling lanes, visible road signs, and traffic control are critical to prevent accidents and make cycling a viable, enjoyable option for all. Road safety measures not only help avoid injuries but also promote confidence among participants, encouraging more community members to embrace cycling as a regular, sustainable transport mode.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
238	Security	Personal or property Crime	1	Property crime may affect cyclists' safety and their sense of security overall. This is only moderately relevant during the event since the event takes place only during the mid-morning hours. However, it is important to consider it as a relevant element whereby preventive measures can mitigate risks and improve overall cycling experiences in Kampala, which is the goal of the Kampala cycling day event. Property crime can be reduced by installing bike racks and secure parking for bicycles at relevant institutions or priority places to begin within the city.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
7	Socioeconomic	Population growth rate	2	Population growth in Kampala influences demand for sustainable transport, increasing relevance, but its impact is hard to determine on a single event day	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
8	Socioeconomic	Income distribution	3	Income distribution is highly relevant because lower-income groups may benefit most from accessible, cost-effective transport modes like cycling, influencing inclusivity in participation.	Kampala	Uganda	Kampala Cycling Day	Early
93	Environment	Noise Pollution	1	Noise levels have little direct impact on the event since cycling is a silent activity. The route chosen for the event is mainly noise free unlike some parts of Kampala where there is so much noise from street vendors and street preachers.	Kampala	Uganda	Monthly Cycling Day	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
94	Environment	Air quality	1	Air quality is crucial, as high pollution levels could affect participants' health and deter participation, making it highly relevant for an outdoor event like cycling. It has however been scored 1 because many people in Kampala do not know this concept, and, or ignore its effect on their health.	Kampala	Uganda	Monthly Cycling Day	Early
2	Culture	Cultural norms	2	Women for a long time were not encouraged to ride bicycles or climb trees which were viewed as habits that devalue them, especially in central Uganda.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
95	Environment	Clean streets	1	One can see waste thrown on the streets on many occasions along the NMT corridor	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
96	Environment	Weather conditions	1	During the rainy seasons, there is a lot of rain, and this leaves many areas of the corridor waterlogged because of the poor drainage system in some areas along the corridor.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
97	Environment	Noise Pollution	3	Many people in Kampala are discouraged to walk along the NMT corridor due to the high noise experienced from various sources including street vendors, preachers, public transport touts, vehicles among others.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
98	Environment	Air quality	1	The daily and annual mean PM _{2.5} concentrations for the entire Kampala city from January, 2020–June, 2022 were 60.4 µg/m ³ and 59.2 µg/m ³ which is approximately 5 and 12 times the daily and annual WHO recommended average PM _{2.5} concentration of 15 µg/m ³ and 5 µg/m ³ respectively (WHO, 2021). This is rated 1 because many Ugandans neither know this, nor mention it as a challenge. But poor air quality discourages people from doing PA, and it is a risk that people exposed to bad air quality will suffer with respiratory diseases.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
5	Infrastructure	Quality of infrastructure	2	There are potholes along the NMT corridor especially around the area close to the Ham and Qualicel buildings. This affects the quality of cycling for those who ride bicycles, it also affects the route picked by those who push wheelbarrow carts whereby they will choose to avoid the big potholes where possible. Furthermore, potholes contribute to the increase in road accidents, and this is especially true along the NMT corridor where the narrowed road is now accommodating the motorcycles (boda-bodas), the pedestrians and cyclists.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
6	Infrastructure	Accessibility and connectivity	2	While the NMT corridor is much appreciated amongst cyclists, the lack of connectivity defeats its purpose. Pedestrians appreciate the NMT pilot corridor because it enables them to access shops downtown where goods are cheap, and it connects to the public taxi parks.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
180	Political	Corruption	2	Corruption was also cited as a factor influencing enforcement of the use of the NMT including allowing street vendors and motorcycles to operate along the NMT corridor and yet it was mainly created to ease access and transportation for pedestrians, cyclists and people with disabilities in Kampala.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
326	Political	Ineffective enforcement	2	While there was much political will and support for the NMT pilot corridor, its effectiveness is affected by poor adherence to the regulations that govern the NMT corridor.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
239	Security	Police presence	2	There are few police officers on sections of the corridor that are farther away from Luwum street.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
240	Security	Personal or property Crime	1	There have been incidents of theft along the NMT corridor whereby amenities such as bicycle racks have been stolen/vandalized.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
327	Security	Police presence	2	Police presence is crucial to ensure the safety of participants, manage traffic, and prevent accidents, making it very relevant for a successful event.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
328	Security	Lighting	2	Security along the NMT corridor is noted to be concerning and there is poor lighting at night due to insufficient or poor lighting	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
9	Socioeconomic	Population growth rate	2	High population growth rate in Kampala contributes to a high demand for non-motorized transport infrastructure in Kampala. This contributes to the high congestion seen at the NMT pilot corridor.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
10	Socioeconomic	Education Level	2	Those with lower education levels are more likely to belong to lower social economic strata and adopt walking as a means to get around.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
11	Socioeconomic	Economic activity	2	Street vendors who commonly use the NMT corridor to display and sell their goods mention that they do this out of necessity, and lack other means to survive.	Kampala	Uganda	Non-Motorized Transport Pilot Corridor	Late
29	City characteristics	Informality-formality	2	Informal occupation of the hills reduces the natural spaces for physical activity, due to Greenbelt fragmentation and privatization. The population living on the hills increased from 26% to 33.9% by 2018.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
30	City characteristics	Topography	3	People living in high-slope areas put in more physical effort to access their homes, which could discourage them from engaging in physical activities on the Greenbelt. Around 70,144 residents, equivalent to 33.95% of the population of Independencia, live in areas with slopes greater than 20°.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
31	City characteristics	City extension	1	This can help determine the amount of infrastructure needed to engage in physical activities, such as the number of green spaces or sports facilities, and improve planning.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
32	City characteristics	District zoning	2	Understanding zoning within and on the surroundings of the Greenbelt is crucial for designing programs to promote physical activity according to landscape type (e.g. lomas ecosystem, tree plantings, and coastal desert).	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
33	City characteristics	District zoning	2	Enables identification of the urban population's location and the areas where sports programs can be implemented to maximize their impact.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
34	City characteristics	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	2	The more accessible the Greenbelt is, the more people can integrate physical activity into their daily routines by utilizing its areas.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
35	City characteristics	Access to basic services	2	Some areas on the hills lack basic services such as water and electricity, which can influence the presence of people along the Greenbelt.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
52	Culture	Identity	2	People from the high Andean regions usually have a close connection with nature or the landscape. This might help with engaging people in activities that require physical effort in the Greenbelt, such as gardening and raising small animals. By 2005, 40% of the population of Independencia was made up of migrants from high Andean regions such as Áncash, Cajamarca, Junín, and Ayacucho.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
53	Culture	Physical endurance	1	People from high Andean regions might have greater endurance for physical activity due to their physiology (better adapted to live in high altitudes), and lifestyle. This is reflected in the fact that some elderly people move through the Greenbelt without difficulty, demonstrating the physical capabilities of this group.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
56	Culture	Migration	2	Recent migration to Lima might have less active participation in the workshops of the intervention.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
55	Education	Environmental awareness	2	Environmental awareness is key to conserving the Greenbelt while ensuring better-quality spaces that promote physical activity. Desert landscapes are often considered "dead" or empty land, frequently occupied by informal and formal settlements.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
61	Education	Educational level	2	People with higher education levels tend to have poor access to physical activities (data from general research). In Independencia, 48.9% of the district's population has a secondary education.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
62	Education	Sportive facilities	1	The installation of sportive courts in the lower parts of the Greenbelt, close to the last row of houses, might stimulate people to go up the hills and access the Greenbelt.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
36	Environment	Thermal sensation	3	High temperatures affect motivation and performance in physical activity. The Greenbelt also receives high amounts of radiation.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
37	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	2	The formation of the lomas ecosystem is related to moisture content (which depends on climatic conditions) and generally occurs during the colder months, from July to October. This creates a green landscape in some areas of the Greenbelt, which motivates people to engage in physical activities such as Eco-routes.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
323	Environment	Heat wave & extreme weather	3	Heat waves are becoming more frequent in Lima and should worsen thermal sensation and heat-related illness in people. (e.g. in 2023, the district reached a heat index of 34°C).	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
104	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	3	Increasing green spaces might motivate more people for practicing physical activities, for instance, due to shading. The indicator of green areas per inhabitant rose from 1.87 to 2.5 m ² per person in the district, due to the implementation of forest parks in the Greenbelt.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
105	Environment	Solid waste	2	The boundary between the hills and urban areas is used as a dumping ground. The presence of waste, especially at the entrance to the Greenbelt, can discourage people from engaging in physical activities in that space.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
106	Environment	Air quality	1	In 2018, high levels of air pollution were recorded in the district. It affects respiratory and cardiovascular health and reduces physical performance.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
193	Governance	Specific normative	3	They facilitate the creation of infrastructure, health programs, and urban policies that encourage public participation in physical activities. There are legislations that require municipalities to implement programs and activities that promote sports and physical activity.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
134	Health	People with NCDs (Non-Communicable Diseases)	3	It allows us to understand the current situation of people with obesity, serving as an indicator to assess the future impact of physical activity programs developed in the Greenbelt. Cases of obesity increased significantly from 2,896 to 5,443 between 2018 and 2021.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
135	Health	Health facilities	1	Collaboration with medical centres could help design strategies to raise awareness about the importance of physical activity and promote its practice, especially among people with medical conditions. There are 11 health establishments available.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
136	Health	Social programs	2	Social programs can improve the economic and health conditions of the local population, promoting better nutrition and enhancing performance in physical activity within the Greenbelt. There are social programs that provide financial and food support to vulnerable individuals, improving their health and well-being.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
221	Infrastructure	Transport network	3	Insufficient road infrastructure limits the mobility of people both within the Greenbelt and in accessing this space, including elements such as stairs, sidewalks, and connections between the forest parks, among others.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
222	Infrastructure	Transport network	2	The lack of regulation in public transportation affects the availability of options to access the Greenbelt, with "mototaxis" being the main mode of transport. This can be a limiting factor for people accessing the Greenbelt to engage in physical activities.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
272	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	3	The poor condition or lack of sports infrastructure in the hills reduces opportunities for physical activity. In the hillside areas, the sports infrastructure is limited or non-existent, and at the district level, the available spaces are underused and lack maintenance.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
273	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	3	Infrastructure (trails, resting areas, and sports equipment) motivates people to engage in outdoor exercise. Initiatives are being carried out to implement the first phase of the comprehensive plan for the Greenbelt of Independencia.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
164	Physical activity	Inactive individuals	1	Given the lack of local information on these topics, it is essential to consider this data when designing strategies to promote physical activity in the Greenbelt. 46.7% of the Peruvian population does not engage in any physical activity.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
165	Physical activity	Workdays	1	Given the lack of local information on these topics, it is essential to consider this data when designing strategies to promote physical activity in the Greenbelt. On average, the working hours range from 9.6 hours, Monday to Friday.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
166	Physical activity	Reasons for not engaging in physical activity	1	Given the lack of local information on these topics, it is essential to consider this data when designing strategies to promote physical activity in the Greenbelt. Citizens of Lima do not engage in physical activity due to lack of time (70% of the population).	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
167	Physical activity	Time spent in sedentary activities during leisure time	1	Given the lack of local information on these topics, it is essential to consider this data when designing strategies to promote physical activity in the Greenbelt. On average, citizens spend around 21 hours per week watching television.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
194	Political	Sports programs	3	The municipality promotes sports and physical activity programs that could be implemented in the Greenbelt, where other activities such as gardening and trekking are already taking place. Identifying these activities is key for designing the intervention.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
195	Political	Political support & funding	3	The implementation of investment projects in the Greenbelt provides an opportunity to improve and enable its spaces, which would contribute to enhancing the quality of these spaces and encourage their use for physical activities. The public investment project profile for the first phase of the comprehensive Greenbelt Plan for Independencia is currently being developed.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
196	Political	Different political backgrounds	2	Generally, when there is a change in authorities there is a tendency to establish different priorities, which can lead to the interruption of environmental and sports projects developed under the previous administration. The Municipality of Independencia has a high turnover of staff and officials.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
58	Political/governance	Implementation of new programs	2	Public willingness for the implementation of tourism services in the district.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
235	Safety	Perceptions of safety	3	It reduces outdoor physical activity and limits operating hours. The main obstacle to accessing recreational activities in Independencia is citizen insecurity.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
54	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	3	Cohesive communities have an active role in maintaining the Greenbelt and stimulating the use of the area.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
57	Socioeconomic	Lack of awareness about the intervention	3	There are people in the district who are unaware of the Greenbelt. Only 53.1% of those surveyed in the Somos Barrio project knew about the existence of the Boca de Sapo park (part of the Greenbelt).	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
59	Socioeconomic	Economic activity	1	The time available and the physical effort a person invests in their workplace can affect their participation in physical activities in the Greenbelt. In the district of Independencia, 37.8% of the population is engaged in commerce, 19.28% in industry, and the rest in other activities.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
60	Socioeconomic	Population economic level	2	It affects people's priorities when carrying out activities. 31.4% of the population is in the 'Low' category and resides in the hills, which could lead this group to prioritize other activities, such as work, over engaging in physical activity in the Greenbelt.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
201	Socioeconomics	Demographics	2	It allows for better planning of the resources and spaces needed for physical activity. In 2017, the district had a population of 211,360 inhabitants.	Lima	Peru	Independencia Greenbelt	Early
107	City Characteristics	Topography	1	Walking on slopes requires more physical effort than in flat areas, so it could influence the level or desire to be active (walking or sports) in the target population.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
63	City characteristics	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	1	Accessibility to the Legacy Sports Complex is essential for more schools and children to practice physical education classes. More than 20 schools have been identified at walking distances (around 100m) to the facility. Nevertheless, safety can be an issue when considered in the context of Villa Maria de Triunfo.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
140	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	1	VMT is the district with the least number of green areas in Metropolitan Lima. The routes the children walk from their schools to the Sports Complex for their physical education classes lack green areas. Some benefits of green areas are the perceived pleasantness of walking and shade during walks, so increasing green areas could improve PA conditions for students and general population.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
99	Environment	Air quality	3	Students walk to the Sports Complex, whose pedestrian entrance is located adjacent to roads with high vehicular traffic, so air pollution can be a risk factor for students. However, there are no monitoring stations nearby and the extent of the problem is unknown.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
100	Environment	Solid waste	1	No solid waste hotspots have been identified around the Sports Complex. However, the green areas are in poor condition and people have been identified as littering in these areas. Students walk along these paths and waste accumulation could be detrimental to their health.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
101	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	1	The district of VMT has lomas ecosystems, which are part of a regional conservation area. Ecotourist activities such as trekking, walks, bird observation, etc. are carried out. Especially during lomas season, from July to October, the area encourages PA, attracting people from other districts.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
102	Environment	Thermal sensation	3	In summer, the routes the students walk lack shade, there are no green areas nearby and the avenues are made of concrete, this characteristic can increase the feeling of heat. On particularly hot days, physical education classes may be cancelled for safety and to protect students from the heat.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
325	Environment	Extreme weather	2	Heat waves are becoming more frequent in Lima and should worsen thermal sensation and heat-related illness in people.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
108	Governance	Level of govt + power on decision	2	In the district the binding levels of government are the local level with the Municipality and schools, and the national level with the Legacy, police and ministries. These levels have specific areas aimed at increasing PA levels in the district. Despite being at different levels of government, these institutions work in an articulated and direct manner.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
120	Governance	Specific normative	1	The intervention has regulatory support for its implementation.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
121	Governance	Level of government and power on decision	3	The main authority in the territory is the district municipality, which has a Culture, Sports and Youth Department that promotes interventions aimed at increasing the levels of PA in the district. They do not currently have a binding role in the intervention, but their addition in the next stages could strengthen it.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
122	Governance	Citizen participation	2	The district has a level of citizen organization and participation that may favour the intervention.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
137	Health	People's health status	3	According to local statistics, the main cause of hospital admissions for children in the district is respiratory diseases. Children's routes to their physical education classes are nearby high vehicular traffic streets, where air pollution can be a risk factor.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
138	Health	People's health status	3	The promotion of physical activity can help reduce childhood obesity statistics in the district.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
139	Health	Health facilities	2	The existing health centres may not be able to cope with the district's population, however, there are no records to indicate this.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
141	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	1	The number of sports areas is insufficient to promote physical activity levels in the population.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
64	Socioeconomic	Type of school (private or public)	3	Private schools are larger in number but smaller in number of students, mainly because of the monthly fees and also the size of the institution. The smaller the institution, the more likely it is that it will not have the necessary facilities to carry out all activities, such as physical education classes.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
269	Socioeconomics	Income distribution population	3	Family income is a condition for children to stay in school. If the child withdraws from school, he or she would no longer benefit from the facilities of the Sports Complex for classes.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
270	Socioeconomics	Access to sanitation	2	Directly influences the health of children and their quality of life.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
271	Socioeconomics	Access to sanitation	2	Directly influences the health of children and their quality of life.	Lima	Peru	Legacy	Late
198	Cultural	Identity	2	Holds sentimental and ideological value, attracting citizens with a historical connection to the event.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
220	Cultural	Identity	3	Slovenia's biggest event that effectively encourages community engagement and active living.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
241	Cultural	Identity	3	The event has evolved from a historical commemoration into a deeply rooted cultural and social tradition, reinforcing collective memory and social cohesion. The tradition's impact shapes urban planning and policy, emphasizing inclusivity and intergenerational participation.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
242	Cultural	Identity	3	Fosters a sense of belonging and strengthens community ties through shared experiences.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
13	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	2	By maintaining accessibility to the trail throughout the year, it encourages daily exercise and promotes an active lifestyle beyond the annual gathering. This shift enhances public health benefits and reinforces the event's long-term impact on urban planning, ensuring that infrastructure supports continuous use. Decision-making prioritizes trail maintenance, safety, and accessibility to maximize its utility for citizens.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
219	Health	Health facilities	3	The event promotes physical activity, addressing a need for more public health initiatives in Slovenia.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
14	Infrastructure	Utilities	2	It increases accessibility and participation; however, it requires ongoing technological updates and administrative resources. Digital enhancements can further improve user experience.	Ljubljana	Eslovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
162	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	2	Regular maintenance keeps the trail in optimal condition, promoting safety and usability year-round.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
163	Infrastructure	Transportation network	2	Limited and inconvenient bus routes reduce accessibility and deter some participants.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
12	Political	Political support & funding	2	By removing financial barriers, the intervention encourages broader participation from a wide range of social groups, ensuring inclusivity regardless of economic status.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
199	Political	Political support & funding	2	Well-funded through municipal support, ensuring sustained event quality.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
200	Political	Different political backgrounds	2	Changes in political leadership may result in decreased funding or support for the event.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
223	Security	Cyclist accident	2	Cyclists on the trail during the event can disrupt pedestrian flow and pose safety concerns.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
243	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	2	Encourages community involvement and skill development through volunteer roles at the event.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
244	Socioeconomic	Social cohesion	3	Engaging different generations is key for mass participation, ensuring inclusivity across age groups.	Ljubljana	Slovenia	Walk along the wire	Late
274	Culture	Religion norms	1	Religion might have less influence on PA than migration and cultural norms. Through, religion could be related to migration background and cultural norms	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
275	Culture	Cultural norms	3	Cycling is associated with cultural background, Haustein et al. (2020) showed that both people from immigrant origin from Western and non-Western background in the Netherlands cycle less than people of Dutch origin. This effect also has a gender component to it, with non-Western origin women cycling less than non-Western origin men. Other hypothesized variables are access to bikes, learning how to cycle, and safe cycling-roads.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
276	Culture	Migration	3	Cycling is associated with cultural background, Haustein et al. (2020) showed that both people from immigrant origin from Western and non-Western background in the Netherlands cycle less than people of Dutch origin. This effect also has a gender component to it, with non-Western origin women cycling less than non-Western origin men. Other hypothesized variables are access to bikes, learning how to cycle, and safe cycling-roads.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
318	Environment	Safe access to green, public and natural areas	3	Regarding the ecological (green blue) structure of Rotterdam, see the map below. Regarding the blue structure, there are two large rivers in Rotterdam (the Muse, and the Rhine), two small rivers (the Schie, and the Rotte), and multiple lakes in the North side of the city. The green structure is more distinct in the North with multiple larger parks. On the South side of Rotterdam, there is a large park. The green structure largely follows the mobility infrastructure, e.g. boulevards or previous train tracks, and does not connect throughout all neighbourhoods. Overschie is situated in an area with blue and green structures, because of this the intervention initiatives already existed (e.g. various community gardens) and they only needed to be connected to form a route. Whereas in Tarwewijk, the area has a less green structure and only neighbours a blue structure, therefore green initiatives first might need to be set up before they can be connected.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
292	Environmental context	Extreme weather	2	Storms will lead to flooding, the green spaces that are created through the green routes act as a water buffer when water in the rivers is at a high level.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
293	Environmental context	Natural Hazards	3	Especially flood risk is seen as high, see storm risk for explanation on how storms and heavy rainfall lead to floods in Rotterdam.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
294	Environmental context	Specific environmental indicators on air, soil and water quality	2	Water quality for potable water is good with a hardness of 8.5DH, for river water there are reports that (toxic) waste is dumped and the water quality is decreasing. For air quality: 21.1 µg/m ³ NO ₂ , 18,9 µg/m ³ PM ₁₀ and 7.7 µg/m ³ PM _{2.5} were measured as yearly average	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
296	Environmental context	Extreme weather	2	An important feature for intervention is to reduce heat island-effect, however heat waves are not happening very often. Though expected to happen more often in future. Outdoor PA is hampered by extreme heat, and the green environments that are being implemented or maintained in the intervention play a role in reducing the heat effects on the city.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
297	Environmental context	Light pollution	2	Green space allows the city to have areas that are less light polluted	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
298	Environmental context	Extreme weather	1	Not known for every natural hazard, for flooding a map exists that shows people would have a part of their house that remains dry. This also contains shared apartment buildings, in that case multiple households must live in the upper apartments.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
299	Environmental context	Biodiversity	3	Creating green routes is important from an environmental perspective to improve climate adaptation, decrease flood risk, and improve biodiversity.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
300	Environmental context	Clean streets	2	Bad air quality can affect residents' motivation to be outdoors (e.g. smog) and has a negative effect on residents' long-term health.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
301	Environmental context	Weather conditions	2	The weather (temperature and rainfall) can influence outdoor activity, and it is likely that people participate less in outdoor activity in fall/winter when temperature is at its lowest and most rain falls.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
320	Governance	Level of government and power on decisions	3	This intervention, and most physical activity interventions, are on municipality level. The municipality shares power of decision making with other actors (see figure)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
321	Governance	Organisation structure health system	2	Through the Social Support Act the municipality becomes an important driver of the intervention. Through organisation of the health system, the GP has a crucial role in patient-contact and is therefore an important stakeholder for the intervention	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
322	Governance	Relationships between departments	3	Three municipality departments are setting up an integral way of working around green and healthy neighbourhoods. Moreover, there are multiple stakeholders involved such as active community members who also collaborate with the municipality departments. (see figure)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
277	Health	People's health status	3	Lower than average Dutch status for some indicators/diseases, e.g. life expectancy. PA is an important determinant for health status.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
279	Health	Health facilities	2	Through the Social Support Act the municipality becomes an important driver of the intervention. Through organisation of the health system, the GP has a crucial role in patient-contact and is therefore an important stakeholder for the intervention	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
280	Health	Nutrition	1	Nutrition is not directly linked, except some initiatives include 'edible gardens', which can help sustain people who are on food-support.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
281	Health	People with disabilities	2	Rotterdam should consider this group and ensure that PA intervention is also accessible to this group.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
282	Health	Mortality rate	1	The mortality rate is low and the focus in health and social care is more on DALY and QALY rather than mortality rate.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
314	Infrastructure	Transportation network	2	<p>The transportation network in Rotterdam consists of car-roads, bike-lanes, and sidewalks for private transport. Shared mobility is possible through small and large electric scooters, and public transport through busses, trams and the Rapid Transit System (metropolitan trains). The access to public transport is unevenly distributed across neighbourhoods, with some neighbourhoods, especially those in the South, have only one bus or tram line coming into the neighbourhood, and no direct connection to the city-centre.</p> <p>Whereas, in the Northern part of the city, some neighbourhoods are very well connected with multiple direct tram, metro and bus lines to the city centre. In Overschie, for example, there is a bus, tram, and metro line connecting the neighbourhood directly with the city-centre.</p>	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
315	Infrastructure	Utilities	1	In general, every house has access to electricity, gas, heating, and internet. Prices for gas and electricity have gone up, so that could hamper accessibility.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
316	Infrastructure	Sport Facilities		Regarding sporting facilities, Rotterdam has 350 sports associations for 60 different sports. There are almost 200 different locations that Sport Company Rotterdam maintains and rents out to the municipality. There is a fund that offers financial support for low-income families with children (under 18 years old) to encourage greater childhood participation in sport.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
317	Infrastructure	Transportation network	3	The quality of infrastructure (rolling stock) is in general good, as it is maintained by the municipality public transport operator (public transport) or municipality (private transport). There has been some criticism of the city's design favouring cars and too little consideration given to walking/cycling. Cycling lanes are not always safe or well maintained, e.g. 60% of cycling lanes meet the safety norms and there is a lack of parking spots for 10.000 bikes in the city centre. Rotterdam residents gave the city a 6.8 for its walkability, with most negative feedback about cars of motorized vehicles, a lack of green or poor air quality. So, in terms of active transport, there could be some improvement to facilitate active mobility. It is possible that the better maintained and safer the active mobility possibilities within the green route in Overschie, the better use residents make of the intervention.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
319	Infrastructure	Welcoming facilities or open spaces	2	The waterfront and some parks are also promoted as venues for active recreation activities. Some other public spaces in Rotterdam are not always perceived as very welcoming, especially in the city centre with big buildings and large open spaces. In neighbourhoods, there are often smaller public spaces such as squares and parks, that are, depending on the neighbourhood, and its' residents, more or less welcoming.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
283	Political	Different political backgrounds	2	The political course under the mayor is not always the same course the alderman wants to take. This ensures continuity but also can cause friction.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
284	Political	Budget cuts	3	Budget cuts on social welfare organizations and volunteering organizations will hamper community-based/co-created interventions.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
285	Political	Political agenda	3	A focus on healthy city supports the development of city-wide health interventions.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
287	Political	Population trust	2	This can hamper co-creation processes with the municipality	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
288	Political	Informality-formality	2	Co-creation is supported by inviting citizens to participate in creation/implementation of policies	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
289	Political	Ideology	1	Background information on city	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
302	Safety	Perceptions about safety	2	The perceived safety feeling in many Rotterdam neighbourhoods is lower than the objectively measured safety. This can hamper outdoor activities, not only from residents but also municipality initiative.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
304	Security	Personal or property crime	1	There were 51.569 crimes in 2020. There are 4 burglaries per 1000 inhabitants (in 2017).	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
305	Security	Terrorism	1	The national threat of terrorism has been raised to 4 (out of 5) since 2023. I still don't think this has (had) an influence on the development or maintenance of the intervention.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
306	Security	Armed conflict	2	More common, especially knife and gun conflicts (often related to drug conflicts and youth conflicts). Guns and knives are regulated in the Netherlands, so still relatively low. Consequently, residents could feel unsafe outside.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
307	Security	Crime rate	1	51.569 per year (in 2020)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
308	Security	Car accidents	2	11.75/1000 inhabitants in 2022, high compared to other Dutch cities. This could lead to residents feeling less safe to use active transport.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
309	Security	No proper safe walkways	2	Rotterdam residents gave the city a 6.8 for its walkability, with most negative feedback about cars of motorized vehicles, a lack of green or poor air quality	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late
310	Security	Adequate road signage	1	There is adequate road signage, also on cycling lanes and around the city centre also for walkers	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschiese	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
311	Security	Police presence	1	There is a normal police presence on the street, there are also street guards, who cannot fine you, but are helping to keep the streets/public spaces safe	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
312	Security	Public systems without guard	1	Almost no public system, except big public transport stations, in the Netherlands has guards, only special circumstances, e.g. threats to mosques or synagogues because of Gaza conflict	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
313	Security	Lighting	1	Relatively good lighting throughout all of Rotterdam.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
329	Socioeconomics	Demographics	2	Rotterdam is the second biggest city in the Netherlands, and therefore an important city in the Netherlands, both for residential and labour purposes.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
330	Socioeconomics	Demographics	1	Relatively equal distribution	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
331	Socioeconomics	Demographics	2	Only 18% of residents are under 18 years and 16% over 65 years old. For the neighbourhood Overschie, this is 16% under 15 years old, and 17% over 65 years old (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024c). For the neighbourhood Tarwewijk, this is 16% under 15 and 8% over 65 years old (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024g)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
332	Socioeconomics	Demographics	2	For the neighbourhood Overschie, this is 16% under 15 years old, and 17% over 65 years old (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024c). For the neighbourhood Tarwewijk, this is 16% under 15 and 8% over 65 years old (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024g)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
333	Socioeconomics	Demographics	3	Physical disability hampers participation in daily life and PA	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
334	Socioeconomics	Demographics	1	Rotterdam does not have informal settlements nor rural areas	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
335	Socioeconomics	HDI indicators	1	For the whole Netherlands, not specifically for Rotterdam.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

ID	Type of element	Element	Level of relevance	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	City	Country	Project name	Intervention
336	Socioeconomics	Access to sanitation	1	Everyone has access to drinking water, there might be a few exceptional cases, but they are not measured	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
337	Socioeconomics	Demographics	1	Only 1.114 people is natural population change, rest is caused by immi/emigration.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
338	Socioeconomics	Income distribution	3	Education level, income level and neighbourhood are connected in Rotterdam, with certain neighbourhoods being lower income and lower educated residents.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
339	Socioeconomics	Education level	3	Education level, income level and neighbourhood are connected in Rotterdam, with certain neighbourhoods being lower income and lower educated residents.	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
340	Socioeconomics	Social cohesion	3	Social cohesion is dependent on the neighbourhood; some neighbourhoods have very active social communities and others have less social cohesion. Citywide the neighbourhood attachment is decreasing, from a score of 103 (out of 200) in 2020 to 95 (out of 200) in 2024 (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024f). 15% of the residents of Rotterdam report to have actively engaged in the community at least once a month in the past 12 months (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024f). In Overschie, the neighbourhood attachment was scored 115 out of 200 and had the same level of community engagement as the Rotterdam average (Gemeente Rotterdam, 2024d).	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late
341	Socioeconomics	Caring Responsibility	1	Lot is unknown of break-down of caring responsibilities in Rotterdam, but in the Netherlands still more women take on caring responsibilities such as children of informal caring responsibilities than men. Source: (Municipality Rotterdam, 2024)	Rotterdam	The Netherlands	De Groene Overschie	Late

The SWOT analysis was conducted in two parts. The first focused on collecting, organizing and ranking differing ideas, opinions and perceptions regarding the four dimensions. After that, the participants were invited to think about strategies by relating strengths- opportunities, strengthens- threats, weakness opportunities and weakness- threats. The following tables presents the SWOT elements recollected in each late intervention, besides the early intervention Independencia Greenbelt, in Lima. The summary is displayed in Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Table 4: Strengths Between Cities Summary

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 1	Community engagement	Combining green and health/multiple value health	Good maintenance of the infrastructure;	Socializing: The event increases interaction and connection between people and groups from different ages and background.	There are pre-approved management instruments related to the Greenbelt Independencia. These instruments allow participation in financial fund competitions aimed at developing the proposals they outline, such as infrastructure improvement, the creation of new forest parks, among others.	The Legacy project (public institution) has a solid organization and state budget.	Positive presence: The initiative creates a positive presence in the living spaces of underprivileged residents, promoting social engagement.	Unique concept: The initiative promotes movement through both individual and group activities, effectively complementing the work of physiotherapists.
Point 2	Job creation	Stakeholders acknowledging the multiple value helps to further develop the intervention	Great location selection whereby there is a high demand for the infrastructure;	Recreation: Being physically active and having fun in a relaxed, communal environment.	Established social organizations exist that utilize and protect the Greenbelt Independencia.	The VMT Sports Complex has multiple sports spaces for various activities.	Community DNA: The kiosk understands the identity of the neighbourhood and is shaped by contributions from various partners and visitors.	Enthusiastic coaches: The coaches are well-trained, motivated, and dedicated to the project, instilling belief in its effectiveness.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 3	Reduced carbon emissions	Not only a focus on physical health, but also mental health (more specifically relaxation)	Having an NMT champion (Amanda Ngabirano)	Cooperation: The event fosters cooperation in different ways: teamwork between participants (e.g. triple race), collaboration between organizers to ensure the flow of the event and engagement with participants and spectators.	There is a decision by the authorities of the Municipality of Independencia to recover the Protection and Landscape Treatment Areas (They are important natural areas with ecological and landscape value, where construction or urban use that could damage their environment is not allowed).	The intervention is applied to private and public institutions without distinction.	Accessibility: The kiosk is open consistently on Tuesdays, offering a reliable resource for the community.	Evidence of effectiveness: There is clear evidence of increased physical activity and high satisfaction among participants, highlighting the program's impact.
Point 4	Proven program success	New initiatives want to join so the network is growing without much effort	Promotion of physical activity,	Very established, easy sign up	The agreement with National Agrarian University La Molina will help strengthen the Greenbelt Independencia.	Legacy and educational institutions work in an articulated manner for the benefit of the student population.		Accessibility: The program is physically and financially accessible, providing straightforward and manageable options for patients.
Point 5	Wide coverage	Name recognition through network structure, some residents attend one participating initiative of De Groene Overschiese and learn there are more initiatives in	reduction of fumes (air pollution) is attributed to the NMT corridor/environmental benefits. Supportive political will (government	It is already traditional for schoolchildren to participate in the event		Legacy provides credentials to students for their entry to the Sports Complex, for greater student safety.		Positive social impact: The initiative has a positive effect on mental health and helps reduce social isolation.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
		their neighbourhood.	funding of the project);					
Point 6	Well-trained staff		Pedestrians can move around with ease	<p>A very recognizable project:</p> <p>WATW is a well-established and prominent event in Ljubljana, associated with its cultural and historical identity, and is familiar to most residents and visitors.</p>		The Police Station has preventive programs that can strengthen intervention.		<p>Clear communication:</p> <p>The website and promotional materials are clear and informative, aiding in public understanding and engagement.</p>
Point 7	Increased budget and bike lanes		Narrow streets/buffers for vehicles; One bicycle parking spot.	<p>Each of the stakeholders contributes their part:</p> <p>Each contributes according to their expertise or resources, such as organizing logistics, maintaining the route, promoting the event, providing funding, or managing safety.</p>				<p>Collaborative opportunities:</p> <p>There are plans for group sessions in collaboration with social organizations, responding to a clear community need.</p>
Point 8	Improved public health		Better shopping experience: The NMT corridor raises the profile of Kampala regionally	<p>Recreation, exercise, socializing, new knowledge:</p> <p>People get to socialize, be physically active and learn more about the city's history.</p>				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 9	Solid structure		Great improvements for pedestrian space;	<p>City Municipality of Ljubljana excels at the whole deal:</p> <p>MOL demonstrates exceptional organizational skills and ensures the smooth execution of events. Participants feel confident in the event's success.</p>				
Point 10	High citizen participation		Greening;	<p>Good informing:</p> <p>Effectively providing participants and the broader community with clear, accessible, and engaging information about the event (sending invitations, informing about starting points and bus routes, logistics, informing through their website about yearly activity and historical significance).</p>				
Point 11	Environmental benefits		Improved pedestrian safety;	<p>Tradition:</p> <p>It commemorates the period when Ljubljana was encircled by</p>				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
				barbed wire during World War II and serves as a symbolic reminder of resilience and freedom. The tradition encompasses not only the annual organization of the event but also its integration into the city's cultural heritage, community involvement, and intergenerational participation.				
Point 12	Public space recovery		Consideration for people who ride bicycles.	Nice trail: The trail is well-designed, scenic, and enjoyable to run or walk on.				
Point 13				Appropriate time of the year: The event has been planned thoughtfully with respect to the environment, weather, and social calendar, ensuring a better experience for participants.				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 14				A meeting of people (See Point 1 socializing)				
Point 15				<p>Mass participation. An incentive for all generations: The event unites people from different generations, creating an atmosphere of community and shared purpose, where everyone feels motivated to take part.</p>				
Point 16				Strong infrastructure and support from municipal services.				
Point 17				Year-round accessibility encourages continuous physical activity and promotes public health benefits.				
Point 18				Free admission ensures inclusivity and broad community participation.				
General Comment				<p>Strengths. The strengths discussion focused on</p>			Revisar bogota	

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
				<p>the positive aspects of the event's tradition and its ability to unite various stakeholders. Participants agreed that the event promotes not only physical activity but also socializing and a sense of community.</p> <p>The ease of registration and cooperation between organizers were also highlighted. The inclusion of specific generational involvement was seen as a key driver of mass participation, and the involvement of the Municipality of Ljubljana (MOL) was particularly noted for its organizational excellence.</p>				

Tabla 5: Weaknesses Between Cities Summary

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 1	Direct impact in all localities	Continuity threatened by lack of shared agency and the vulnerable structure of the network	Lack of continuity: the pilot NMT corridor is a 1.8km non-motorised road in the central business district of Kampala. It starts abruptly and ends abruptly, and is not connected to other pedestrian walkways, yet. This is challenging for those who would like to cycle or walk along this corridor.	There is no public bus circular transport, so that we do not return by the same route	There is a lack of budget to implement projects, which is related to the shortage of human resources, logistics, and personnel for the maintenance of green areas.	The list of actors participating (educational institutions) is small. Currently, only 3 schools participate in the program. One of the reasons for this is the lack of dissemination of the programme through various channels, which makes it difficult for educational institutions in the area to get to know it.	Funding constraints: The financial resources required to maintain operations are significant, and political support is crucial for sustainability.	Sustainability issues: The program is currently not sustainable, relying heavily on external funding and partners.
Point 2	Lack of storage space for road safety items	Lack of shared agency by initiatives participating in De Groene Overschiese	Limited protection of pedestrians; street vendors; Boda-boda encroachment	Walking in "one direction" (then back along the same path) --> e.g. for the ones walking just shorter distances	There is a lack of ecological and civic culture among the population, leading to inadequate dissemination of the Greenbelt Independencia.	Cessation of intervention due to mass sporting events, e.g. when there are events such as the Pan American Games or the Olympics, the sports complex is closed, and other activities are suspended.	Volunteer dependence: There is a reliance on volunteers, which can lead to inconsistencies in service and commitment levels.	Unfamiliarity: There is a significant lack of awareness about the initiative among referrers and patients, impacting referral rates.
Point 3	Lack of coordination at sub-	Network structure is vulnerable,	Modes of transport which compete and not communicating with each other	Crowded in some places: Along the event route there may be a higher	In many cases, the municipality experience delays in delivering	Entry to the Sports Complex requires notification at least one day in advance, so	Limited operational hours: Being open only once a week limits accessibility	Resource limitations: Time and resources are often insufficient, and

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
	directorate level	initiatives can fall away		concentration of people, making the space feel congested or busy. This can affect the overall experience of the event, as participants might feel squeezed or less able to enjoy their surroundings or engage in activities freely.	projects to the residents, which negatively affects their perception of the institution.	parents who wish to accompany their children (especially those with special abilities) for certain events cannot enter.	for those in need of immediate assistance.	the turnover of coaches can disrupt continuity.
Point 4	Lack of long-term planning		Poor enforcement of regulations along the NMT corridor; Abuse of the NMT	Occasional vandalism along the path	Sustainability of the project overtime (Due to the fact that many projects do not continue because of a lack of budget or personnel)		Location: Although the location has positives, it is also a location that doesn't always have positive connotations, and so people might not be inclined to go there (too far from Turnhoutsebaan).	Non-binding referrals: Patient participation is non-binding, leading to challenges in ensuring commitment to the program.
Point 5	Insufficient formalization of the volunteer program		Public mindset does not appreciate NMT	Lack of a system targeting specific vulnerable groups for participation				Monitoring challenges: There is a need for more precise monitoring of outcomes, including referral effectiveness and the program's reach.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 6	New motorized vehicles on bike routes		Limited to only one location	The path requires ongoing maintenance and security measures to ensure safety and usability				
Point 7	Presence of pets on bike lanes		Poor communication and marketing of the infrastructure to the public and stakeholders					
Point 8	Shortage of human resources		The area is too busy and has too much commercial activity					
Point 9			The NMT corridor limits movement of bulky goods; Poor maintenance; Rampant corruption					
Point 10			As boda-bodas riders, we were not planned for (left out of the plans)					
Point 11			No bicycle parking lot: Part of it still allows vehicles; It is congested/busy location					
Point 12			high reliance on donors and government funding					

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
			could make this unsustainable or slow;					
Point 13			misuse by the community and the NMT is not connected to the main road.					

Tabla 6: Opportunities Between Cities Summary

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 1	Circular economy	City-wide roll-out of social prescription might lead to more healthcare organizations being interested in referring their patients	Attention increased on climate change/air pollution.	<p>Organized invitation for parents and grandparents of the participating schoolchildren:</p> <p>The MOL and Timing could directly invite parents and grandparents to increase participation.</p>	Implementation of the first phase of the Greenbelt Independencia project (The project aims to improve the Greenbelt with modular infrastructure, an irrigation system with treated water for reforestation, and educational activities and environmental brigades to promote the circular economy).	Institutional support to strengthen the management of the Legacy, for example, the Peruvian Institute of Sport (IPD), ministries, NGOs, among others.	<p>Enhanced partnerships:</p> <p>Leveraging existing networks to strengthen community ties and improve service offerings.</p>	<p>New financing models:</p> <p>There is potential for structural financing through government initiatives and new payment models (e.g., flat-rate practices /"forfaitaire praktijken").</p>

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovía	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 2	International investment	The Social Overschiese (a similar map with social organizations in the neighbourhoods) This strengthening of the social structure of the neighbourhood is viewed as an opportunity to link up with more social organizations, and an opportunity for shared funding	Road safety. Advocacy for road safety and emphasis by implementers/enforcers to ensure that pedestrians walk safely is ongoing in a way, thanks to the NMT corridor	Cycling event on Wednesday (By bike along the route): This specific day allocation helps ensure cyclists have a dedicated time to enjoy the route without interfering with pedestrian activities on the other days.	Develop strategies through agreements with public institutions, private entities, or NGOs that will consolidate ongoing projects and enable funding acquisition. An example is the willingness of private companies (Social Responsibility and Carbon Footprint).	The Citizen Participation Office of the Police Station can support the dissemination of the program and involve more schools.	Online presence: Developing a website and utilizing social media platforms to increase visibility and attract funding.	Enhanced collaboration: Building connections between various healthcare providers and promoting the role of nurses in referrals can alleviate pressures on GPs.
Point 3	Key stakeholder education	Collaboration neighbourhood approach (new municipality strategy) sees De Groene Overschiese as example for their approach and the participants mentioned showcasing the intervention as leading in this field and in Rotterdam, which is an	Opportunity for bicycle businesses as well as an opportunity to promote equality and inclusivity. Inviting women to ride along the NMT corridor for example promotes physical activity, boosts confidence, and enables access to transport solutions for women to promote financial empowerment.	Entertainment for students at the end of the hike or at individual checkpoints: One of the methods to increase student participation and enhance their experience, ensuring the continuation of the tradition.	Economic opportunities for the population (If more projects are developed in the Greenbelt and it becomes a more popular destination, the district's population could seize the opportunity to open various businesses.)	Political interest in the sporting growth of the country.	Mobile kiosk initiative: Exploring the possibility of a mobile kiosk to reach different neighbourhoods and address varied community needs.	Educational initiatives: There is an opportunity to educate both healthcare providers and patients about the program to increase familiarity and trust.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
		opportunity for recognition.						
Point 4	Income generation opportunities	Development of City Park West would incorporate many initiatives from De Groene Overschiese, leading to improved visibility and a stronger sense of agency by advocate organization of City Park West in De Groene Overschiese.	Pilot project; this shows that Non-motorized streets are possible/Benchmark for increasing the network.	Workshops for a healthy lifestyle: Opportunity for health professionals to educate participants about the importance of physical activity and maintaining overall well-being.		The Legacy's ability to host diverse activities and programs (e.g., guided tours, organic gardens) so that it becomes a breeding ground for talent.		Integration into medical records: Integrating the program into electronic medical records can streamline referrals and improve engagement.
Point 5	Innovate with complementary activities	Collaboration health sector - there is a national trend towards social prescription, green & health, and neighbourhood level interventions. Participants mentioned the health sector becoming more open to the development of	Involvement of cycling organizations and other partners interested in NMT to advocate for NMT spaces and gather evidence on its benefits.	Entertainment for children at the end of the hike: One of the methods to increase children participation and enhance their experience, ensuring the continuation of the tradition.				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
		interventions like De Groene Overschiese.						
Point 6	Measure happiness levels	Based on point 5, participants hoped that more national funding opportunities would become available	Pilot project help to draw lessons for improvement. Creation of awareness.	Separate - bike riders after main events (See point 2, the difference is the date that is reserved only for cyclists).				
Point 7	Connect more bike routes and lanes		Continuously showcase the benefits of the NMT to the community to enhance appreciation	Various workshops: It can also be creative workshops. (See points 4 and 9).				
Point 8	Strengthen citizen participation		Creating Non-Motorized Transport infrastructure in other places either residential or commercial i.e. some industrial parks where most factory workers walk to work.	Presentation of societies: Various federations, associations, societies and communities can share their activities and engage with participants, fostering connections and raising awareness about their missions. It provides an opportunity for participants to learn about new				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpen	Antwerpen
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
				initiatives and become more involved in community efforts.				
Point 9	Enhance educational approach		CSOs and private organizations for green mobility and health	Add points of interest (e.g. famous people, musicians): A method to enhance the cultural and creative aspects of the event while creating lasting memories for the younger generation, encouraging them to carry on the tradition in the future.				
Point 10	Create green corridors		Speed management policy to reduce speeds on roads like Kampala road.	Creating an interactive map on the website, providing information about bus connections.				
Point 11	Promote bike lane benefits and attract users		The NMT corridor could extend the much-needed cycling network.	Potential for further development, including additional recreational features and community programs.				

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovía	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 12			It is now a liveable city.	Potential for further digital enhancements to improve user experience and data tracking.				
Point 13			There are development partners.					
Point 14			The presence of academia interested in this, as a field of research.					
Point 15			Scaling up to a wider coverage.					
Point 16			Funding opportunities.					
Point 17			Construction of fly-overs to decongest the place.					
Point 18			Getting new technology.					
Point 19			NMT mindset change campaign. Promoting cycling and walking					
Point 20			Climate change is a good opportunity for NMT projects. Promote public health.					
Point 21			The government has created an enabling environment through the NMT policy.					

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpen	Antwerpen
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 22			Urban road design manuals that incorporate NMT infrastructure.					
Point 23			Greening. Health and wellness are promoted as people use the NMT corridor.					
Point 24			Providing non-motorized transport solutions					
Point 25			Marketing to the general public and specifically people working and living around the NMT.					
Point 26			Technological advancement.					
Point 27			Expanding public transport options.					

Table 7: Threats Between Cities Summary

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 1	Political will	End of current funding (provided by the healthy and active living agreement)	High volume of commercial motorcycles (known as Boda-bodas), commercial minibuses (dominant commercial public transport in Kampala and Uganda)	Weather: Poor weather can cause logistical disruptions and safety risks, leading to participant discomfort and ultimately resulting in reduced attendance.	There is no budget, which is due to the lack of support from state ministries and a lack of political will.	Weather factors, for example, rain causes the suspension of classes at the Legacy for safety reasons (slippery tracks, no coverage in the sports infrastructure).	Communication gaps: Ineffective communication can hinder collaboration with partners and limit outreach efforts.	Limited government support: There is no clear ownership or commitment from the local government, which could undermine sustainability.
Point 2	Insecurity	Another potential threat are key figures leaving the intervention. Participants mentioned the possibility of the neighbourhood manager leaving the neighbourhood due to internal changes in the municipality or by choice.	Informal businesses, Street vendors	Change of mayor: New leadership may have different political ideologies or focus areas, which could result in reduced financial resources for community initiatives, including sports and recreational activities.	Invasion of the Greenbelt Independencia and the associated issues (Increase in population, reduction of Greenbelt spaces, among other factors)	Change of management due to elections, both at the municipal and national level. This can paralyse programmes or delay administrative procedures.	Volunteer engagement: A potential decline in volunteerism due to 1) a growing individualistic culture and 2) lack of continuity (open only once a week) could impact service delivery.	Perceptions of coaching: The trend of 'coaches' in society could undermine the program's credibility and perceived value.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 3	Lack of citizen culture on road safety	Intrinsically motivated people fall away: due to other priorities or stress. De Groene Overschiese relies heavily on key figures who find this intervention important, but it is not per se structurally embedded and embraced by all stakeholder organizations to support its continuity.	Focus on road design for motorized transport	Decline of participants over time: if younger generations fail to internalize the tradition and significance of the event, unlike older generations who have a deeper understanding and connection to its historical meaning, there is a risk for long-term sustainability of the event.	Lack of accessibility. (Currently, access to the Greenbelt is limited to the entrances of human settlements and, in addition, it is far from the public transportation system. Therefore, private vehicles are the main means of transportation to reach the area.)	Walkability of the routes, for example, traffic lights on the routes the children walk, support for safe crossings, no green areas, air pollution, noise pollution, etc.	Political climate: Changing political views may affect ongoing support for community initiatives. Also depends on the government at both city and district level, post-election. Sometimes used as political football.	Time constraints: Shortages of time and resources among partners, including GPs, can hinder the program's effectiveness.

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerpn	Antwerpn
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 4	Changes in administration		Limited engagement with public/ politicians and other stakeholders to raise profile and importance of NMT (mindset change).	Risk of vandalism and environmental wear for long-term upkeep.		Citizen insecurity and delinquency, which is accompanied by student gangs, micro-drug trafficking, student desertion and alcoholism in adolescents.	Actual climate: Very sensitive to weather circumstances (too hot/cold or wet à issue for community workers & general approachability of the kiosk)	Collaboration challenges: Difficulties in collaboration between different organizations and staff can limit operational effectiveness.
Point 5	Shifts in mobility trends		Lack of security along the NMT corridor; Poor visibility: high air pollution and dust.	Technical failures, data security concerns, or administrative inefficiencies could disrupt participation.		Health epidemics, for example, population isolation measures may suspend face-to-face classes and thus the involvement of schools in the intervention. In addition, the Sports Complex may close its facilities.	Lack of planning permission: Risk that it cannot remain due to its temporary nature.	
Point 6	Lack of adequate infrastructure		Not-so profound policies to support continuation.			Childhood malnutrition can affect students' performance in physical education classes, as well as		

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
						walking short to medium distances.		
Point 7	Route suspension due to construction		Commercial motorcycle riders (boda-bodas)' unruly behaviour			The VMT Sports Complex is under public administration, so if the country is selected to host a mass sporting event, these facilities will be used and closed for the intervention and the general population during the period of the event.		
Point 8	Coexistence with users' pets		High risk and incidence of accidents.					
Point 9	Adverse weather conditions		Misuse of the facility					
Point 10	Pressure from interest groups		Enforcement challenge (day and night)					
Point 11			Mindset acceptance is lacking. Residents of Kampala have not yet accepted that the NMT corridor is					

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschiese	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
			only for walking and cycling.					
Point 12			Misuse of the NMT corridor. High influx of commercial motorcycles (boda-bodas) in the area					
Point 13			Funding gaps; Theft of funds allocated to the maintenance of the NMT corridor					
Point 14			Corruption/Influence peddling					
Point 15			Inferior quality work on the NMT as evidenced by presence of potholes, and faded markings on the zebra crossing.					
Point 16			Political Opportunism. Political leaders who have interfered with the enforcement of the NMT guidelines because of their desires to garner support from voters who include those who misuse the					

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschie	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
			corridor such as street vendors, and commercial motorcycle riders.					
Point 17			Lack of mass transit systems in Kampala.					
Point 18			Ever-growing para-transit modes such as Boda-Bodas; Over-population in Kampala					
Point 19			Increase in the number of vehicles in Kampala					
Point 20			Poor public transportation					
Point 21			There is poor security of bicycles due to lack of sufficient bicycle parking					
Point 22			Competing funding priorities;					
Point 23			Land conflicts with community members;					
Point 24			Competition from ride hailing services;					

City	Bogota	Rotterdam	Kampala	Ljubljana	Lima	Lima	Antwerp	Antwerp
Intervention	Ciclovia	De Groene Overschie	NMT	Walk AT Wire	Greenbelt	Sports Complex	Health Kiosk	Exercise Prescription
Point 25			Lack of policy support and regulation					

4. GENDER – INCLUSIVITY – DIVERSITY (GID)

The GAPPA makes specific reference to assisting in the achievement of a number of 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) including Gender Equity (SDG5) and Reduced Inequalities (SDG10). Therefore CITY-MOVE aims to assess the degree to which city interventions are helping to address equality, inclusivity and diversity amongst certain community groups known to be insufficiently active - these are women, older adults, people living with disability and those from lower socio-economic communities. To do this, a theoretical framework (Delbaere et al., 2024) designed to address the components and intersections of gender, inclusion, and diversity (GID) was applied during the assessment workshops. Two tools were used, the GID checklist and the GID monitoring form. The GID checklist is used by CITY-MOVE researchers to document categories of inclusivity and to monitor how these may change over the life-course of the project and how we are accommodating for diversity in our meetings. The purpose of the GID monitoring form is to gather information on how representative the people who attend CITY-MOVE workshops and meetings are of the city's population they represent.

4.1 GID RESULTS

Most of the CITY-MOVE contact points focused on inviting for the assessment workshop, the stakeholders who represented the most relevant organizations for the intervention. This happens mainly because of the difficulty in guaranteeing the participation of at least one person per organization. Nevertheless, in general, a balance between female and male representatives was reported in most of the workshops. Moreover, in the case of Kampala, the organizers followed a more restricted route in order to accommodate GID demands during the workshop. In this case, it was possible to achieve a balance between male and female, besides the participation of vulnerable groups, including a person with a declared physical disability.

5. REFERENCES

- Delbaere, B., Pereira Barboza, E., Van Rafelghem, E., Potter, K., McCabe, E., McBeth, Á., Utkarsh, S., Rudd, K., Fernandez de Osso Fuentes, M.J., Duarte, A., Gäckle, J., & Keune, H. (2024). The development of a Gender, Inclusion and Diversity Framework for inclusive Nature based Solutions in cities. *Research Directions: One Health*. 2, e1, 1-7. DOI: 10.1017/one.2023.14
- Petkovic, J., Magwood, O., Lytvyn, L., Khabsa, J., Concannon, T. W., Welch, V., Tugwell, P. (2023). Key issues for stakeholder engagement in the development of health and healthcare guidelines. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 9(1), 27. DOI: 10.1186/s40900-023-00433-6
- Ennis, G. & West, D. (2010). Exploring the Potential of Social Network Analysis in Asset-based Community Development Practice and Research, *Australian Social Work*, 63:4, 404-417, DOI: 10.1080/0312407X.2010.508167
- Hoffmann, T., Glasziou, P., Boutron, I., Milne, R., Perera, R., Moher, D., Altman, D., Barbour, V., Macdonald, H., Johnston, M., Lamb, S., Dixon-Woods, M., McCulloch, P., Wyatt, J., Chan, A., & Michie, S. (2014). Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. *BMJ*. 348:g1687.
- Vagias, W. M. (2006). Likert-type scale response anchors. Clemson International Institute for Tourism & Research Development, Department of Parks, Recreation and Tourism Management. Clemson University. <https://media.clemson.edu/cbshs/prtm/research/resources-for-research-page-2/Vagias-Likert-Type-Scale-Response-Anchors.pdf>
- World Health Organization. (s/f). STAKEHOLDER MAPPING GUIDE: Mapping potential key stakeholders in reproductive health and family planning service delivery, in preparation for implementing WHO MEC/SPR guidance, from <https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/reproductive-health/contraception-family-planning/stakeholder-mapping-tool.pdf>
- Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018–2030: more active people for a healthier world. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/272722/9789241514187-eng.pdf>

CITY-MOVE

City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health

HORIZON-HLTH-2023-DISEASE-03

DELIVERABLE 1.3 - SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

STAKEHOLDER ASSESSMENT AND CORE CONTEXT ELEMENTS GUIDE v3

WP1

Authors: Taícia Marques and Ruth Lowry

Summary Sheet

Deliverable Number	D 1.3
Deliverable Name	Supplementary material- Stakeholder Assessment and Core Context Elements Guide
Full Project Title	CITY-MOVE: City based interventions to stimulate active movement for health
Responsible Author(s)	Taícia Marques ¹ , Ruth Lowry ²
Contributing Partner(s)	¹ Universidad Nacional Agraria La Molina; ² Ulster University
Peer Review	-
Contractual Delivery Date	June 30 2025
Actual Delivery Date	-
Status	-
Dissemination level	Open access
Version	v.3
No. of Pages	43
WP/Task related to the milestone	WP1/ Task 1.2 and 1.3
WP/Task responsible	WP1/ Taícia Marques
Document ID	
Abstract	-

Legal Disclaimer

CITY-MOVE is funded by the European Union (EUROPEAN HEALTH AND DIGITAL EXECUTIVE AGENCY-HADEA, GAP-101136358) and Innovate UK (10109214). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, Horizon EU or Innovate UK. The granting authorities can be held responsible for them.

Table of Contents

List of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
List of Abbreviations	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. DEFINITIONS	7
1.1. Stakeholder(s).....	7
1.2. Engagement.....	7
1.3. Categories of stakeholders.....	7
2. STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING	10
2.1. How to fill the stakeholder map table.....	12
3. GENDER – INCLUSIVITY – DIVERSITY (GID)	13
4. CORE CONTEXT ELEMENTS	13
4.1. Relationship with other Work Packages in City-Move	14
4.2. Which are the core context elements we need to look for in City-Move?.....	14
4.3. City-Move GAPPA Mapping.....	17
5. FACILITATING STAKEHOLDER ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP	18
5.1. Facilitator Preparations for Stakeholder Assessment Workshop.....	19
5.2. Checklist.....	20
5.3. Informed Consent	20
5.4. Ground Rules Suggestions.....	20
5.5. Questions and Introductions	21
6. CONDUCTING THE STAKEHOLDER ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP	21
6.1. Stakeholders map validation	21
6.2. SWOT Analysis	26
7. REFERENCES	30
8. ANNEXES	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: GAPPA Interventions Mapping - Working Example from the City of Antwerp.....	18
Figure 2: Representation of "The Spider's Web"	23
Figure 3: A1 size paper should be divided into 3 equal parts and the title of the intervention.....	24
Figure 4: Classification of stakeholders inside key, primary or secondary groups, according to their importance or power to the intervention.....	24
Figure 5: Frequency of engagement.	25
Figure 6: Stakeholder influence.....	26
Figure 7: Suggestion of SWOT Analysis representation	28
Figure 8: (SO & ST) Strategies and (WO & WT) Strategies.....	29

List of Tables

Table 1: Stakeholder categories and their descriptions with examples	7
Table 2: Data Collection tool 1.1- Stakeholder map table.....	11
Table 3: Core context elements table.	14

List of Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
GAPPA	Global Action Plan on Physical Activity 2018-2030
GID	Gender, inclusivity and diversity
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
NGO	Non-Government Organization
PA	Physical Activity
SAW	Stakeholder Assessment Workshop
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Why this guide?

The WP1 is in charge of creating a cross-contextual framework to replicate health interventions in cities that may contribute to the reduction of non-communicable diseases cases. Five different activities are related to the work-package, two of them **T.1.2 -A stakeholder assessment and analysis in each city for each intervention** and **T1.3 -Core context elements**, will be partially filled with the information collected in each intervention, by following this guide. Also, an equity analysis will monitor gender, inclusivity and diversity (GID) in the stakeholder analysis (T1.2) and might be considered as part of the core elements mapped on T1.3.

The aim of this guide was to provide City-Move research team with a source of information on what evidence needs to be collected, how and why. The purpose here was to create consistency in the processes used between interventions, cities and countries. The Guide presented as a Supplementary Material of Deliverable 1.3 has been updated based on the feedback received from City-Move research team after its application in each of the six cities studied.

Where to apply this guide?

We recommend the application of the complete guide to the **late interventions**. With regard to the **early interventions**, we suggest the assessment workshop is skipped for now, since the co-creation process will be conducted during WP2 activities. Nevertheless, to prepare for the WP2 work, we recommend you complete the intervention's stakeholders mapping activity, the core context elements and the GAPP context analysis. This information should be reported to WP1 as well.

1. DEFINITIONS

1.1. Stakeholder(s)

People and groups who are **responsible for or affected** by health, healthcare-related decisions, physical activity interventions and physical activity-related decisions.

Stakeholders may include, not only those directly involved in the development of guidelines, policies, strategies, planning and implementing the interventions, but also those involved in preparing research, conducting research, dissemination activities or implementing that evidence.

Stakeholders can:

- Identify problems, prioritize solutions, design context-specific interventions.
- Get involved in the implementation or delivery of interventions.
- Mobilize beneficiaries to engage with interventions or be the beneficiaries.

Please note that we would view beneficiaries as part of the stakeholders group. They are represented by (urban) citizens, community members, clients/patients, patient caregivers, patient or community advocates/ organizations and the general public (see Table 1). Apart from receiving the benefits from involvement in the intervention, they may also have an active role in designing, setting up, delivering, monitoring and evaluating physical activities interventions.

1.2. Engagement

A bi-directional relationship between the stakeholder and researcher that results in informed decision-making about the selection, conduct, and use of research.

1.3. Categories of stakeholders

The eleven categories of stakeholders listed on Table 1 were initially adapted from the work of Petkovic et al. (2023). The original reference was developed for health systems, while City-Move interventions involve more sectors than health, such as social services, community development, urban planning, transportation and infrastructure. Therefore, a preliminary list was shared with City-Move researchers and, after the application of the Guide in each city, categories were reviewed and adjusted to incorporate the majority of possible types of stakeholders that are part of City-Move interventions.

Table 1: Stakeholder categories and their descriptions with examples

Stakeholder category	Description	Examples (please fill free to expand this list)
Payers or Funders of research	Individuals and organizations that fund research projects , such as government funders, industry funders, foundations	- National research funding agency - Philanthropic foundation

Stakeholder category	Description	Examples (please fill free to expand this list)
Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers	Individuals, organizations, and entities that pay for health services and prevention projects . Payers / Purchasers / Funders/ Financers of Services and prevention projects i.e. health, community development or urban planning and urban design.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public health systems - Private insurers - Financing stakeholders of public sectors (can be different sectors, health, transportation, built environment, infrastructure, social sector etc.) -Private financing / private enterprises - Social security agencies - Event partners who donate or partially finance the intervention
Policy makers	Individuals, organizations, and entities that craft public or private policy (of relevance to the City-Move Intervention) at any level of government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regulators (city, regional or national levels) - Ministries - City governors such as mayors, council member, city departments, local councils, etc.
Researchers	Individuals, organizations, and associations that conduct related research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trial manager - Data collector - Field researcher - Systematic reviewer - Study manager
Product developers	Individuals or organizations working manufacturing pharmaceuticals, medical devices, medical procedures, health technologies, or for profit educational and behavioral packages. Includes producers and/or developers of interventions/products and tools for health, and prevention and Physical Activity (PA) such as assisted devices, active transportation, sport and leisure equipment and clothing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pharmaceutical company - Medical device manufacturer - Digital / Guided programs available for purchase (e.g., cognitive behavioral therapy programs) - Apps for PA monitoring - Sport equipment manufacturers - Leisure clothing manufacturers
Program managers	Managers/directors who plan, lead, oversee, or deliver any prevention and/or program or activities that provides attractive and green public spaces, active mobility, healthy environments, public health, community services, education, clinical care or sport and leisure services (e.g., budgeting, hiring, staffing, organizing, coordinating, reporting) focused on improving health, social	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May be health care providers but are not those on the front-line delivering health care related to the program of interest. -Urban planners, environmental, greening, climate, sustainability, housing departments or similar.

Stakeholder category	Description	Examples (please fill free to expand this list)
	inclusion, quality of life and wellbeing of city citizens.	-Social, educational and sport departments.
Providers	Persons and their professional association who provide individual health care and prevention, social care, sporting and PA practice in a professional capacity and allowed by regulatory bodies to provide a service that includes support for carrying out physical and sporting activities.	- Psychologists, clinical pharmacists, nurses, physiotherapists, dentists, optometrists, physician's assistants, physicians, optometrists, physical educators, personal or group trainers, rehabilitation specialists, social care
Active community members and organizations	Individuals in the general population (e.g. citizens, neighborhood representatives) or civil society organizations (e.g. NGOs) who play an active role in designing, setting up, delivering, monitoring and/ or evaluating PA interventions or have a role as advocacy groups.	Member of the city's public who is involved in the decision-making elements of the intervention or advocacy for PA.
Patients, patient caregivers, patient advocates/organizations	Those with lived experience of non-communicable diseases or who care for or advocate on behalf of those with lived experience (older adults, disability, women, and children); they might also play an active role in designing, setting-up, delivering, monitoring and evaluating PA interventions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patient with NCD on which the guideline is focused - Caregiver of patient on which the guideline is focused - Member of a Patient group representing patients on which the guideline is focused.
General Public	Individuals in the general population (e.g. citizens, neighbors) of a defined geographic area excluding patients, caregivers, and health professionals living or working with NCD. Those members of the public NOT accounted for in a previous category; NOT actively involved in the designing, setting up, delivering, monitoring and evaluating PA interventions	Member of the public with no specific experience with NCD and not actively involved in decision making.
Logistics or support	Any institution or individual, external to the intervention, that might bring any kind of logistic, communication, promotion or other support to improve the operationalization of the intervention.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Local commissary, traffic inspectors - First aid attention -Local business selling food, drinks or another kind of goods that may support PA practice

Source: adapted from - Petkovic et al. (2023). doi: 10.1186/s40900-023-00433-6.

2. STAKEHOLDERS MAPPING

Stakeholder mapping is the process of identifying, visualizing (diagramming), and prioritizing stakeholders by analyzing their role, engagement, influence and interest in a project. It is a way for the research team to learn what interests and/or perspectives they bring to be integrated on cities physical activities interventions.

The objective of the stakeholder mapping is to support our progressive comprehension of inter-organizational governance structures within each CITY-MOVE intervention. This includes understanding the intervention’s assets (other stakeholders involved in the intervention), identifying asset roles and asset-to-asset relationships, at each intervention phase.

We suggested making one map for each City intervention. There may be an overlap (shared stakeholders) between interventions within the City, but that will be explored later at the analysis stage. For early interventions, it is possible that much of the descriptive information regarding roles and responsibilities cannot be filled yet.

The stakeholder's map is a living tool. It can be adapted during the project, especially with information regarding the people that represent each stakeholder group (e.g. snowballing from initial contacts) and the relationship between them.

The “**Data collection tool 1.1 Stakeholder map table**” (Table 2) was the first format used to start mapping who is/are responsible for or affected by the intervention. It is suggested that individuals who have been identified as the City-Move Contact Points will complete the table, in close collaboration with their contact persons in the city and the support of the information collected by applying the “**Data collection tool 1.2 Open interview guide**” (Annex 1), observations and information collected during non-structured conversations. The table provided can be edited to add as many rows as you need.

Table 2: Data Collection tool 1.1- Stakeholder map table

1. Code	2. Name of the institution/ organization	3. Name of the contact person/s (title and level)	4. Contact details (email, phone number, other)	5. Type of organization (Public/ Private/ NGO/ other)	6. Role in the intervention and phase	7. Level of involvement in the intervention (high, medium, low)	8. Relationships with other stakeholders (provide names or codes)	9. Relationships related to GAPP	10. Kind of relationship with other stakeholders (Collaborative, co-operative, problematic, neutral)	11. Explanation
1										
2										
4										
5										
6										
7										

An overview of which content should be filled in each column is presented below:

Column 1: Code

Each team can define a coding system for each stakeholder group to assist in organizing the information and compiling the data in the table. You can decide how to do so. This might be a separate number or code from the ones used to anonymize people involved in the project, according to ethics.

Column 2: Name of the institution/ organization

Fill in the full name of the institution/ organization and its acronym if it exists.

Column 3: Name of the contact person/s

Complete name of the contact person, with their title and position within the organization.

Column 4: Contact details

Include the email, phone number and any other contact details you think are important to enable you to approach the person when needed (e.g. working hours or days).

Column 5: Type of organization

Indicate if the organization is public, private, a Non-Government Organisation (NGO aka not-for-profit) or other (specify what “other” means for each case it appears).

Column 6: Role in the intervention and phase

Specify the role the organization has in the intervention, according to Stakeholders Types presented in Table 1, and the phase it became involved, for instance, the proposal, design, operation and management or monitoring of the intervention. The same stakeholder might have different roles and participate in different stages of the intervention. Please report as much information as you have to capture the various roles held by the organization or sub-divide the organization to separate out the various roles different parts of the organization play in the intervention.

Column 7: Level of involvement in the intervention

Here you should indicate if the level of involvement, or influence of the organization in the intervention is *high*, *medium* or *low*. This information will be interpreted by the researchers after a search on documents and consultation with specific stakeholders during the interviews (tool 1.2) or non-structured conversations. An explanation of the level of involvement can be placed in column 11.

Column 8: Relationships with other stakeholders

This content is key to understanding who is involved in and interacting with the governance of the intervention. You should identify the purpose of this relationship (e.g. finance recruitment, infrastructure, work force). Also indicates how long the relationship between stakeholders has existed, when it started, how it has changed overtime (if known).

Column 9: Relationships related to GAPP

When inputting the information in the table, please indicate which GAPP domain (society, people, environment or system) this relationship signifies. Be aware that the relationship may support more than one GAPP domain, please record all relevant domains. You can provide names or codes of other stakeholders.

Column 10: Kind of relationship between stakeholders

This item reflects the quality of the relationship between the stakeholders mentioned in column 8, and should be filled with *Collaborative / Positive, Contentious / Negative or Fragile*. This information will be extracted from the interviews (tool 1.2) and observations made by the researcher during non-structured conversations. Therefore, this information might be qualitative and subjective. **This sensitive information should be kept internally by the City-Move researcher team** and might be used as an “alert sign” when reuniting controversial stakeholders in workshops and meetings throughout the project.

Column 11: Explanation

In column 11, you can provide any further information or explanation you think will enrich the stakeholders map and analysis.

2.1. How to fill the stakeholder map table

First provide the city and the intervention. Start completing fields 1 to 6. These fields provide information on the stakeholder named and a broad understanding of their role in the intervention. You should follow a snowballing process that starts with the first person(s) identified by each City’s Contact Points when mapping the stakeholder. The next stage is to approach identified stakeholders to see if additional stakeholders are identified, this process is repeated till no new stakeholders are reported.

To confirm information in column 6 and keep filling column 7 onwards, we suggest you apply **tool 1.2- Open Interview Guide** and/or **conduct non-structured conversation with the different stakeholders**. For that, it will be necessary to identify the person(s) to whom it will be relevant to interview or talk. Looking back to the full list of stakeholders mapped, you should ask two main questions:

What do I want to know?

Who might be able to bring me the information I want to get?

This will help you to narrow down the stakeholders' groups and people to define whom you want to interview. Examples can be the head officer of a certain organization, or somebody with substantial responsibility for the implementation. Some organizations are large and complex; therefore you may find that there are multiple stakeholders within one organization, you will need to decide if they provide distinct contributions to the intervention and therefore they should be coded as separate stakeholders. Be aware that the language and terms that we use within CITY-MOVE may not match that of the people you are interviewing, therefore clarify terminology during the interviews (more information can be found on Annex 1 Tool 1.2- Open Interview Guide).

It is important to consider that the same stakeholder group can play different roles, so in cases such as this, mention all of these roles and explain what is involved. Column 11 is where you can give your own explanation, or details that do not seem to fit in other columns.

Once you have a comprehensive map, you should be able to select the stakeholders' representatives who can be contacted in order to validate and enrich the map during a stakeholders assessment group session (Section 5). We reinforce that, in the case of a conflictive relationship between stakeholders described during the mapping, **it should be kept internally by the City-Move researcher team** and might be used as an “alert sign” when reuniting controversial stakeholders in workshops and meetings throughout the project.

3. GENDER – INCLUSIVITY – DIVERSITY (GID)

The GAPPA makes specific reference to assisting in the achievement of a number of 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) including Gender Equity (SDG5) and Reduced Inequalities (SDG10). Therefore CITY-MOVE aims to assess the degree to which city interventions are helping to address equality, inclusivity and diversity amongst certain community groups - these are women, older adults, people living with disability and those from lower socio-economic communities. To do this we will be using a theoretical framework (Delbaere et al., 2024) designed to address the components and intersections of gender, inclusion, and diversity (GID).

The purpose of the **GID checklist** is to document categories of inclusivity and to monitor how these may change over the life course of the project and how we are accommodating for diversity in our meetings (Annex 2). The purpose of the **GID monitoring form** is to gather information on how representative the people who attend CITY-MOVE workshops and meetings are of the city's population they represent (Annex 3).

4. CORE CONTEXT ELEMENTS

GAPPA relates physical activity to a few of the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), recognizing there are multiple policies that can be implemented to promote PA in urban environments (GAPPA, 2018). In CITY-MOVE, each intervention, from each city, might follow a particular route to a more active society, environment, people and system. The **T1.3 - Core context elements** is an activity that proposes researchers step back in time to understand the intervention through a multi spectral lens by knowing the conditions that lead or motivated the design and development, delivery and evolution of the intervention. These conditions are made by different types and arrangements of context elements, and can be social, cultural, geographical, political, economic and so forth. Information might have been collected in distinct documents and during interviews using tool 1.2. Consider that context is dynamic and can change over time. **Try to describe relevant changes in context or for instance, how the intervention can change the context itself.**

A comprehensive understanding of the external forces acting upon each intervention within each city should be achieved. Also, we should try to identify **key uncertainties** that are relevant for the implementation of the intervention.

Based on that, and to facilitate the collecting and reporting of the information, we prepared three guiding questions:

- D. What are the conditions that lead or motivated the design and development, delivery and evolution of the intervention?
- E. Which can be considered relevant changes in context OR how the intervention can change the context itself?
- F. Which are the key uncertainties that are relevant for the implementation of the intervention?

4.1. Relationship with other Work Packages in City-Move

As one activity of CITY-MOVE (WP3), the Template for Intervention Description and Replication (TIDieR) was applied to the late interventions. The TIDieR is a guide reporting checklist developed to improve the completeness of reporting, and ultimately the replicability, of interventions on health (Hoffmann et. al, 2014). The purpose of identifying core context elements in late interventions is to comprehend the drivers and the complexity that might create barriers or opportunities to change.

Early interventions will be developed in CITY-MOVE as Living-labs through co-creation (WP2). To frame the problem effectively and to present a collective solution, researchers will need to understand the context and how it relates to the stakeholders. A first evaluation will be made during year 1 of CITY-MOVE, and a second during year 4, in order to validate and compare the core context elements.

In order to also understand GAPPA context in each city, WP7 suggests you graph and describe the activities each intervention addresses in relation to 20 principles of GAPPA. You can start by using the information from the stakeholder mapping (see column 9). In addition to the CITY-MOVE inventions, please map other relevant examples of PA interventions in the city, which are not the focus of CITY-MOVE, and relate them to GAPPA.

4.2. Which are the core context elements we need to look for in City-Move?

With the inputs from all the WPs, received during the Bogotá meeting (May, 2024), we defined a list of elements that might help researchers in understanding the intervention. The list is not static and the items within each of them can be skipped or complemented, depending on each intervention. To facilitate the visualization of the entire set of core elements and how much they are relevant for the intervention, we ask you to fill in Table 2.

Table 3: Core context elements table.

Element	Type of element	Level of relevance. (1- little relevance; 2-relevant; 3-very relevant)	Explains the level of relevance (why it has been rated 1, 2 and 3)	Source of information
Example: Culture	Religious norms	3	Do not allow women to ride a bike	Ethnographic Study on Gender Norms in Urban Mobility, University of Global Studies (2022)

•

- Socioeconomic: expresses the socio and economical condition of people in the city.
 - Number of people (percentage of men, women, children 0-18 years old, elderly people living with physical disability).
 - Number of people living in urban (formal and informal areas) and rural areas
 - Human development indicators (e.g. Human development index-HDI)
 - Number of people with access to sanitation (drinkable water, sewage system and garbage collection/ recycling)
 - Population grows rate
 - Income distribution population
 - Education level
 - Social cohesion
 - Caring responsibility

- Culture: in case there are any cultural aspects that should be relevant for a health intervention including gender and diversity and inclusion.
 - Religious norms
 - Cultural norms
 - Migration
 - Identity

- City characteristics
 - Population density in the city (hab x hectare; compactness)
 - City extension (hectares)
 - Geography (e.g. hilly or flat landscape, m.a.s.l.)
 - Soil use/ coverage (e.g. % urban, rural, natural)

- Health
 - Peoples health status (e.g. predominance of different diseases, such as NCD, respiratory or endemic mosquitos)
 - Health facilities (e.g. presence and access to hospital, clinics, or family doctor)
 - Nutrition (e.g. health problems related to nutrition)
 - People with disabilities (don´t access physical activities equitably)
 - Mortality rate

- Political
 - Different Political backgrounds
 - Budget cuts (priorities for physical activities interventions)
 - Political agenda
 - Corruption
 - Population trust
 - Informality - Formality
 - Ideology

- Environment (including climate risk)
 - Man made hazards (any kind of human intervention that might result in contamination, landslide or other risks to people)
 - Seismic (e.g. earthquakes and tsunamis)
 - Storm risk
 - Natural Hazards (e.g. flooding, landslides)
 - Specific environmental indicators on air, soil and water quality
 - Vector diseases (related to climate change)
 - Heat waves
 - Light pollution
 - Accessibility (to an environmentally safe place)
 - Biodiversity
 - Clean streets (e.g. presence of garbage on public spaces)

- Safety: refer to a condition where someone or a thing is protected from causes that are likely to cause harm to them
 - Perceptions about safety

- Security: means protecting organizations/people against threats/danger
 - Civil unrest (e.g. protest demonstrations, strike actions)
 - Personal or property Crime
 - Terrorism (e.g. local, national or transnational)
 - Armed conflict
 - Crime rate (e.g. personal and property)
 - Car accidents (e.g. involving pedestrians, cyclists or other drivers)
 - No proper safe walkways
 - Adequate road signage (foot paths, crossing, bike lanes and parking)
 - Police presence
 - Public systems without guard
 - Lighting

- Infrastructure
 - Transportation network (e.g. active mobility, private and public)
 - Utilities (e.g. access to electricity, gas, heating, internet)
 - Sportive facilities
 - Quality of the infrastructure (roads)
 - Accessibility and connections
 - Welcoming facilities or open spaces

- Governance*
 - Level of government and power on decision
 - Organization structure of the health system on different levels (indicates whether public or private in each level)
 - Relations between departments (e.g. Ministry of Health working together with the Ministry of Housing) and local city departments.

*For this specific element/ domain, we ask you to provide an organigram that clearly expresses the multilevel organizational system related to each specific intervention case in CITY-MOVE.

The above information will be useful for the understanding of each intervention and should be collected previously to the assessment workshop. During the workshop, a SWOT analysis session will be conducted in order to assess the stakeholders perspective regarding internal strengths and weaknesses and external opportunities and threats for the intervention. The detailed guide for the SWOT activity is described on section 6.2.

4.3. City-Move GAPPA Mapping

The early and late interventions we focus on in CITY-MOVE are part of a bigger city context in which much more is happening. In the project text, we said that we would generate lessons on a *comprehensive* approach to city-GAPPA, studying the 13 interventions (which come from all GAPPA domains) *and considering the other city-GAPPA interventions occurring in 6 cities*. To do this, WP7 would like to map each of the 13 focus interventions against the 20 types of intervention activities identified in the GAPPA framework, and visualize any linkages of the 13 focus interventions to other GAPPA interventions that are ongoing in the city (see example in Figure 1).

To complete this mapping element, we are asking for you to:

- Map your **early and later intervention** against the GAPPA framework multi-layer figure
- Make a vertical bar for each intervention (early in light blue, late in more purple ~ proposal early/late)
- Link the intervention(s) with the appropriate GAPPA interventions (multiple possible) using lines
- Identify other GAPPA-relevant interventions in the city. Potential resources for this: table 2 in the EU proposal (overview of many interventions in each city), Bogota WP6 slides, your own local knowledge
- Use the 4 boxes (~GAPPA domains) in the right side of the figure to write them down with a short name: assign them the right letter
- Look for relevant links between your early/late intervention and these other interventions
- Use lines to visualize these links
- Provide a text explaining the figure, either in word or in the notes pages under the slide
- You can use the TIDIER text and your own context knowledge to start and deepen it.

Figure 1: GAPPA Interventions Mapping - Working Example from the City of Antwerp

5. FACILITATING STAKEHOLDER ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP

Based on the data collected using **Data collection tools 1.1 and 1.2**, the researchers will have an overview of the organizations, institutions and its representatives that are part of the collaborative process proposed by City-Move in regard to each city intervention. The next task is to make contact with and arrange a Stakeholder Assessment Workshop (SAW) with key stakeholders. We suggest this activity should be conducted with the **late intervention stakeholders**. For the early intervention, workshop guides provided by WP2 should be combined in order to make the co-creation process more time efficient and effective for cities (to be known during Q4 2024).

We recognize that each researcher will need to work with the intervention stakeholders to make these arrangements and therefore we are not stipulating one procedure to do this.

As an important step of workshop preparation, the invitations might be made, ideally by email, with an official letter from the researcher (CITY-MOVE contact point). Nevertheless, previous contact by phone, WhatsApp or direct/ personal communication is also possible. The researcher should choose the most effective way to invite and guarantee the participation of the stakeholders in the workshop. Also, it is important to consider the GID indications available on Format CITY-MOVE - Gender, Inclusion and Diversity Checklist (Annex 3).

Take time in advance to make the invitations and be sure to confirm, if needed, a few days or weeks before the event. Researchers may need to liaise with the organization to understand the most appropriate way of organizing an event and how the invitation should be issued.

We estimated that each workshop should be conducted with approximately 6 to 10 people, but you may be asked to include more. In this case, you will need support from another researcher and can divide

the larger group into two smaller groups (who will complete the task separately before coming together to share and combine their information).

Once the workshop is finished, the researcher should classify the types of stakeholders according with the list provided in *Table 1: Stakeholder categories and their descriptions with examples*.

Below you will find a set of suggestions and orientations to prepare and conduct the SAW. In Annex 5 we provided more tips that might help you successfully completing the task.

5.1. Facilitator Preparations for Stakeholder Assessment Workshop

Your role as a Stakeholder Assessment Workshop facilitator is very important.

Your ability to:

- Make everyone comfortable.
- Encourage everyone to speak up.
- Enforce a respectful tone.
- Managing the pace will determine the quality of the discussion and therefore, The information you gather.
- Consider taking a note-taker and an audio-recorder. A note-taker allows you to focus your attention on the discussion while also ensuring accurate notes.

Pre-Meeting Checks

- Consider a pre-visit to work out the logistics.
- Have a list of materials and ensure you have all the “kit” you need.

Preparing the room

- Arrive early with your note-taker to set up the room.
- Refreshments.
- Post plenty of signs so participants can find their way to the space.
- Test your recording equipment or other electronic equipment to be sure it works.

Opening the session

- Introduce yourself, your assistant, and the purpose of the SAW.
- Explain to participants that they have been invited to share their opinions and that you will guide the discussion by asking the group to reflect on specific questions.
- Tell them what time the session will conclude.
- Address informed consent.
- Address Ground Rules.

5.2. Checklist

- Copies of Participant Information Sheets and Consent Forms (2 signed and one retained by facilitator and one by participant)
- Contact details for Participants (phone numbers)
- Signage and hanging putty (Sticky / Blu Tack)
- Parking Permits for Self (note-taker) and Participants
- Focus group protocol
- Note taking template
- Clip board (can be used as writing surface for self and note-taker)
- Tape recorder and microphone or mobile recording device
- Computer, Projector, Extension cord, cables
- Pens and markers
- Sticky Notes
- A1 Sheets
- Name tents or name tags
- Timepiece – phone or watch
- Flip chart and masking tape (may be used if generating ideas/lists)
- Water/snacks (plates/napkins)
- Incentives (Gift certificates)

5.3. Informed Consent

- Reminder to have read and retained the Participant Information Sheet (see City-Move Consent as a reference for ethics procedures in each country).
- Sign the Informed Consent Form (countersigned by researcher).
- Reminder of the right to withdraw throughout.

5.4. Ground Rules Suggestions

The next stage is to address the ground rules to be observed during the SAW. You can ask the group to generate a list. Below are some typical rules that have been used in this type of research and you can use some of these if you think the generated has not addressed all aspects.

- Confidentiality – please respect it for all our sessions and discussions together
Help protect others' privacy by not discussing details outside the group.
- All mobile phones should be turned to silent or turned off.
- The SAW will be conducted in a manner which is respectful of all participants and their contributions.
- All responses are valid—there are no right or wrong answers
- It's all right to abstain from discussing specific topics if you are not comfortable.
- Participants should focus on answering the questions from their own perspective and should not make judgements on other participants' answers.

- 'I agree – it's the same for me' or 'My scenario is very different to that' but these sorts of comments should be deliberately short and should not veer into judgment on another participant's setting or situation.
- Participants should not seek to offer advice to others within the SAW.
- One person speaks at a time and participants listen attentively to each other.
- Ideally, everyone contributes throughout the SAW but there is no obligation on any participant to answer any question to which he/she is not happy to respond.
- The facilitator may have to interrupt colleagues or bring a topic to a close to ensure time is managed effectively
- Participants should be mindful and patient with other members who may not be conversing in their first language.
- The focus group will be recorded and transcribed.
- The contributors' names will be anonymised in the transcript
- Jargon terms and abbreviations should be explained and preferably avoided where not needed
- De-brief: feel free to contact the facilitator after the meeting if you have concerns over material shared.

5.5. Questions and Introductions

- Allow time for questions after establishing the ground rules
- Name Tags
- Then ask participants to introduce themselves.

6. CONDUCTING THE STAKEHOLDER ASSESSMENT WORKSHOP

One workshop per intervention should be conducted with the purpose of validating and complementing the data collected (stakeholder mapping and context core elements). It will support the development of the initial cross-contextual Theory of Change related to the four GAPPA domains.

6.1. Stakeholders map validation

The preparation for the workshop should follow the suggestions provided in “5. Facilitating Stakeholder Assessment Workshop”. Here we are going to present the structure of the event you might organize with the stakeholders' groups in your city.

6.1.1 Reception of participants and opening session

Prepare the room to receive and register participants **30 min before the starting time**.

People might fill in their name and sign an attendance list of participants before entering the room, with basic information, such as complete name, organization, phone/ e-mail contact. Each participant will receive a tag with their name and organization, that should be placed in a visible place. You might provide refreshments at the start to allow you time to work with people as they arrive.

Also, this is the time to distribute a folder with key documents, such as:

- Information sheet about City-Move (e.g. fact sheet)
- Informed Consent Form
- Participant Information sheet

Once everybody is well settled in the room, it is time for you to open the session. It should take **between 5 to 10 min.**, where you should:

- Introduce yourself, your assistant, and the purpose of the SAW.
- Explain to participants that they have been invited to share their opinions and that you will guide the discussion by asking the group to reflect on specific questions.
- Introduce a key stakeholder to briefly explain the intervention (should be coordinated in advance)
- Tell them what time the session will conclude
- Address informed consent (you may provide them with about 5 min to be able to read, sign and deliver the informed consent)
- Present the Ground Rules.
- Allow time for questions after establishing the ground rules

6.1.2 Ice-breaker

This activity should take about 15 minutes.

Ice-breaker strategies can be used with the objective to encourage group integration and cohesion, develop communication and active listening skills and stimulate reflection on teamwork, recognizing the importance of empathy, collaboration and mutual support.

As City-Move is a project based on a co-production process, we recommend "The Spider's Web" as an introductory game to start building a network of collaboration between the different groups of stakeholders responsible for each intervention.

In "The Spider's Web" participants stand up in a circle and throw a ball of wool at random, introducing and sharing something about themselves with the group. Each time a participant introduces themselves, they create a "spider's web" by holding the yarn and throwing it to another person, encouraging collaboration and mutual support among group members (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Representation of "The Spider's Web"

At the end of the presentations, the facilitator can conclude the dynamic by encouraging the participants to form a collaborative network, just like the spider's web they have just created. It is also possible to reflect that they should look after their relations, because if a participant (or organization) does not feel comfortable or part of the co-production process and "lets go of his or her woolen thread", the spider's web - the group - would break.

To finish the dynamic, the woolen thread is collected in reverse order, going over the qualities of each participant in reverse order.

Considerations:

It should be emphasized to each participant that, once they take hold of the woolen thread, they cannot let go until the dynamic is over; otherwise, the spider's web will break.

It should be noted that when a partner is presenting, the others should remain silent, listening attentively to what he/she wants to share with us.

6.1.3 Validating the Stakeholders Map

This activity should take approximately 30 min.

This exercise should validate and enrich the information collected in Data collection tool 1.1 Stakeholder map table, especially from column 6 to 8. **We suggested confidential or possible conflictive information collected during the interviews (tool 1.2), are kept out of the discussion.**

The names of the stakeholders invited should be written on small sticky paper tabs (of the same color).

A A1 size paper should be divided into 3 equal parts and the title of the intervention (see figure 3). Each part of the paper will represent a **level of power**: key stakeholders, primary stakeholders and secondary stakeholder, where:

- **Key stakeholders:** are able to influence the project, through their skills, knowledge or/and position of power. Their absence or dissatisfaction can cause not only a negative effect but also the possible rejection and end of the project.
- **Primary stakeholders:** are involved in the project directly, through technical and financial support. Their absence would have a negative effect on the project.

- **Secondary stakeholders:** the participation of these stakeholders in the project is only indirect or temporary. Their absence would not have a negative effect on the project. They might be stakeholders who wish to participate more and have different roles.

The stakeholders will be invited to place their tags on the A1, respecting the **level of power** they think is the most feasible. Once the task is completed, the facilitator should ask them to verify whether there is/are other stakeholder that has/have not been considered yet. If so, their name should be written in a different color sticky paper and placed according to its importance for the intervention.

Figure 3: A1 size paper should be divided into 3 equal parts and the title of the intervention

The second task will be to ask participants to organize, from the left to the right in the A1 paper, the level of importance of each organization or institution for the intervention. They should do this in order, first, the classification of key stakeholders, then the primary and finally the secondary stakeholders (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Classification of stakeholders inside key, primary or secondary groups, according to their importance or power to the intervention.

Once the stakeholders are organized in A1 paper, it is time to ask participants to indicate the kind of relation that exists between them. This is a stage where the researcher might use their skills as a facilitator to manage possible conflicting episodes.

The purpose of this task is to describe and summarize the information that each intervention is willing to share rather than evaluate and judge what the interventions are doing. For that, there are two levels of engagement: 'advice/feedback' and 'decision-making'.

'advice/feedback'- includes communication and consultation. Stakeholders receive information or provide their views, thoughts, feedback, opinions or experiences to the intervention; without a commitment from the intervention developers to act on this information.

'decision-making'- includes collaboration and co-production. Stakeholders are engaged to influence the production of the intervention with direct control over decisions OR are equal members of the intervention development team and have a key role in decision-making.

How to measure the engagement?

The Likert scales have been adapted to measure the kind of relationships with stakeholders described above: 'advice/feedback' and 'decision-making'. The scales vary from 1 to 5; 1 representing the weakest relationship and 5 the strongest.

For the 'advice/feedback' the scale will measure **frequency**, where:

- 1 = Very Rarely
- 2 = Rarely
- 3 = Occasionally
- 4 = Very Frequently
- 5 = Always

Researchers should ask participants: **How frequent the communication or consultation happens in the intervention?**

Figure 5: Frequency of engagement.

In order to measure ‘decision-making’, we propose to evaluate the **level of influence** each stakeholder have, where:

- 1 = not at all influential
- 2 = slightly influential
- 3 = somewhat influential
- 4 = very influential
- 5 = extremely influential

Researchers should ask participants: **How influential is your organization in the intervention?**

In case participants are also composed of citizens or community members that are not representing an organization, you might adapt the question to fit the audience better.

Figure 6: Stakeholder influence

During this exercise participants do not need to share any explanations on why they choose some specific answer. By the end of the activity, the facilitator might **open 20 min. for conclusions discussed** with the stakeholders and can ask if someone would like to share any thoughts about the results.

6.2. SWOT Analysis

The second part of the workshop should be dedicated to a collaborative **SWOT** analysis. This activity might take around **60 min.** to happen.

6.2.1 What is a SWOT Analysis & why are we using it?

SWOT stands for: **S**trengths, **W**eakness, **O**pportunities, **T**hreats. The SWOT method was originally developed for business and industry, but it is equally useful in community health and development work. A SWOT analysis helps us to guide the stakeholders to the internal strengths and weaknesses (S-W) of their intervention activities, as well as broader opportunities and threats (O-T) that influence the current or future delivery. Developing a fuller awareness of the interventions will help the stakeholders make decisions about immediate and future activities.

6.2.2 What potential insights are we looking for?

We have chosen the SWOT Analysis to provide CITY-MOVE researchers with an inventory of the city interventions activities; what they see as existing strengths and weaknesses that reveal priorities as well as possibilities. The SWOT allows the stakeholders to:

- Explore possibilities for new insight or solutions to problems with current delivery.
- Make decisions about the best direction for future delivery.
- Identify directions and choices regarding opportunities for success in the context of threats.

6.2.3 How to Conduct the SWOT Analysis

- There are several steps and at each stage you have a leading question to gather information from those involved followed by a sorting task and discussion.
- Think of it as a *Post-it Note* exercise where you are asking them to note ideas and then these are sorted.
 - You can sort by frequency (to identify the common views and collapse similar points into themes to reduce the amount of information)

There are also online tools (if you want to use a virtual board to test run before your session to ensure you know how it works)

- <https://www.well-sorted.org/index.php>
- <https://padlet.com/> - Graffiti Wall feature
- <https://miro.com/>

6.2.4 Planning Phase

- Similar to the mapping exercise you will need to prepare the session in the same manner:
 - You will act as a facilitator to keep things moving and on track.
 - Consider a note-taker to support you to keep track of the time for each stage, record the audio of the meeting and retain and digitize all material.
 - Gain consent from all before you start
 - Let all participants introduce themselves.
- Identify 4 spaces where you can display / gather and collate the 4 elements. This might be 4 spaces on a wall or 4 tables.

6.2.5 Delivery Phase

- Introduce the SWOT method and its purpose to the group. This can be as simple as asking, "Where are we, where can we go?"

STEP 1 S-W – “let’s first look at the various elements of the intervention – What are the Strong (positive) and Weak (negative) elements?”

STEP 2 O-T – “next we want to look at factors outside of your intervention – What are the Opportunities we could incorporate into ongoing work and what threatens current and future work?”

- Give the participants 20-30 minutes to write down their ideas / fill out their own strengths, weakness, opportunities and threats
 - Typically use 4 different coloured Post-it-Notes, one for each element
 - Ask them to record individual thoughts on each note.
- Encourage them not to rule out any ideas at this stage (good ideas emerge from lots of ideas!)
- Once ideas have been generated, they should post them collectively on the display space (wall or table), see figure 7.

Figure 7: Suggestion of SWOT Analysis representation

- Collect and organize differing ideas, opinions and perceptions of the agreed list. This will be a discussion to negotiate the ranking so allow about 20 minutes to complete this task.
 - The strongest to weakest strengths.
 - Most to least dangerous weaknesses.
 - Biggest to smallest opportunities.
 - Worst to least threats.

Potentially if you are limited for time the SWOT exercise (generation of points) could be completed prior to the meeting so they start with the discussion and generate the top list.

- Then move onto the intersection solutions – repeat the same exercise as above
 - Individually or in small groups of 3, generate ideas (20 minutes)
 - come to a collective agreement for each intersection. (20 minutes)

STEP 3 - (SO & ST) Strategies – “Now we want to explore what strengths we can use to take advantage of opportunities and what strengths we can use to avoid threats”

STEP 4 - (WO & WT) Strategies – “Now we want to explore what opportunities can be taken advantage of to overcome weaknesses and what strategies we can use to minimize weaknesses and avoid threats” (Figure 8)

Figure 8: (SO & ST) Strategies and (WO & WT) Strategies

Finally, collect all the generated material and close the session.

7. REFERENCES

- Delbaere, B., Pereira Barboza, E., Van Rafelghem, E., Potter, K., McCabe, E., McBeth, Á., Utkarsh, S., Rudd, K., Fernandez de Osso Fuentes, M.J., Duarte, A., Gäckle, J., & Keune, H. (2024). The development of a Gender, Inclusion and Diversity Framework for inclusive Nature based Solutions in cities. *Research Directions: One Health*. 2, e1, 1–7. DOI: 10.1017/one.2023.14
- Petkovic, J., Magwood, O., Lytvyn, L., Khabsa, J., Concannon, T. W., Welch, V., Tugwell, P. (2023). Key issues for stakeholder engagement in the development of health and healthcare guidelines. *Research Involvement and Engagement*, 9(1), 27. DOI: 10.1186/s40900-023-00433-6
- Ennis, G. & West, D. (2010). Exploring the Potential of Social Network Analysis in Asset-based Community Development Practice and Research, *Australian Social Work*, 63:4, 404-417, DOI: 10.1080/0312407X.2010.508167
- Hoffmann T, Glasziou P, Boutron I, Milne R, Perera R, Moher D, Altman D, Barbour V, Macdonald H, Johnston M, Lamb S, Dixon-Woods M, McCulloch P, Wyatt J, Chan A, Michie S. (2014). Better reporting of interventions: template for intervention description and replication (TIDieR) checklist and guide. *BMJ*. 348:g1687.
- Vagias, Wade M. (2006). Likert-type scale response anchors. Clemson International Institute for Tourism & Research Development, Department of Parks, Recreation and Tourism Management. Clemson University.
- World Health Organization. (s/f). STAKEHOLDER MAPPING GUIDE: Mapping potential key stakeholders in reproductive health and family planning service delivery, in preparation for implementing WHO MEC/SPR guidance, from <https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/reproductive-health/contraception-family-planning/stakeholder-mapping-tool.pdf>
- Global action plan on physical activity 2018–2030: more active people for a healthier world. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

8. ANNEXES

ANNEX 1. DATA COLLECTION TOOL 1.2 OPEN INTERVIEW GUIDE

Selection of stakeholders for open interviews

The first input for Part 1. is the “Stakeholders Map”, (resulted by the application of the “Data Collection Tool 1. 1. Stakeholders map table”). The objective of this mapping activity is to have an overview, for each City, of the types of stakeholders (see fields 1 to 4), the role stakeholders play in the intervention (see fields 5 and 6) and the relationship between named stakeholders (see fields 7 and 8).

The identification of the person(s) to be interviewed will happen through a snowballing process that starts with the first person(s) identified by each City’s Contact Points when mapping the stakeholders. The next stage is to approach identified stakeholders to see if additional stakeholders are identified, this process is repeated till no new stakeholders are reported.

Two main questions will guide what you will ask in the interviews and your selection of who you will interview:

1. What do you want to know?
2. Who might be able to bring the information that you want to get?

This will help you to narrow down the stakeholders' groups and people to define whom you want to interview. Examples can be the head officer of a certain organization, or somebody very much involved in the in the implementation. Some organizations are large and complex, therefore you may find that there are multiple stakeholders within one organization, you will need to decide if they provide distinct contributions to the intervention. Be aware that the language and terms that we use within CITY-MOVE may not match that of the people you are interviewing, therefore clarify terminology during the interviews.

Preparing the interview

The next step is to prepare an your own adapted interview guide. It can be based upon this template but have additional questions organized according to the following steps. Bring for each interview the Informed consent form (see annex ethical protocol). Start each interview with -an ice-breaker at the beginning followed by your main questions, and have probes for each question^[1]. The main issues are identified in this template, but you will have to think about how to formulate your own questions in order to get the information from your respondent. Record the interviews where possible, and use automated transcribing tools (such as transcribing in MS Teams). Try to do the interview with two persons: one interviewer, and one observing, note-taking, recording.

The interview guide has 2 major content parts: It is not necessary to do both parts for all interviews. You can select the relevant parts for the stakeholder you interview.

1. **Part on Role and relations of stakeholders.** This part is meant to validate information from part 1.1 and to complement it. It will provide input for the network analysis and community asset mapping planned in WP1.
2. **Part on the interventions and core components.** This part is meant to collect data to feed the Theory of Change about the interventions and about priorities for process and outcome indicators. This will provide input for building the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis Framework. For the second part of the interviews, you might prefer to interview technical staff and staff involved at operational level for your interviews.

Interview guide

Date	
Place	
Respondent	
Interviewer	

I. Opening remarks and informed consent

Explain purpose of interview, study and ask for consent.

II. Icebreaker

Part 1. Role and relations of stakeholders

III. Understanding the type of stakeholder and their role in the intervention

Questions here should validate the information indicated in the Stakeholders Map.

- Type of stakeholder: understand the organizational structure of the organization or institution
- How is the organization/ institution organized and managed?
- Role in the intervention: understand the broad role of the organization (if exists) and its specific role in the GAPPA intervention at stake
- What are the roles the organization/ institution has related to health interventions? How do they apply to the specific interventions on City-Move?

IV. Understand the relation with other stakeholders

Here the interviewer should also validate the information provided in the Stakeholders Map, asking questions such as:

- With which organizations does your organization collaborate or have to deal with?
- What aspects of the intervention do both organizations collaborate on?
- How do you evaluate collaboration (eg. Collaborative and co-operative, problematic, neutral)?
- Can you identify any additional stakeholders that were not initially considered?

V. Understand if and how gender and equity are addressed

Here we have two elements to address:

- Is there a gender and equity policy that is part of the organization/ institution protocols of functioning? If so, how does it work?
- How the contribution of the organization/ institution to the intervention helps in reducing gender and equity gaps?
- How are so-called 'protected characteristics'^[2] taken into account

VI. Understand governance (or identifying governance models) and participation

Two sets of questions: the first set for people in leading positions and a second set for other people. Depending on the stakeholder, you make a choice these questions.

Set for people in directorate / lead positions who have an overview of the intervention.

- Governance models:
 - o During the planning, designing, implementation and monitoring phases of the intervention, how was/is the governance shared between the stakeholders? Which stakeholders participate and what were/ are their roles? Which are the objectives of the governance scheme that is currently applied?
 - o Are the beneficiaries of the intervention part of the governance structure? What is their role?
 - o Is there any transparency strategy? What kind and how information is communicated?
- Decision making mechanisms:
 - o What are the decision-making mechanisms and how are they incorporated into the governance tools used?
- Participation (not necessary governance):
 - o Is there any mechanism of participation? How does it work? Who participates?

Set of questions for for beneficiaries or stakeholders who do not have much power over decisions.

- Perception of governance models:
 - o Do you know how the intervention is managed? Who is in charge?
 - o Do you think there is a horizontal and transparent way to contact and inform intervention organizers?
 - o Do you think you are heard during decision making processes?
- Participation (not necessary governance):
 - o (If there is a mechanism of participation) Do you think the mechanism of participation is effective? How do you judge successful or effective participation?
 - o Are you satisfied with this mechanism?

Part 2. The interventions and core components

This part will feed the initial theory of change. Before the interview, the researchers have probably already collected information about the intervention from formal documents and websites etc available, through fact gathering. From the results, specific interviews will be defined in order to validate and in-depth knowledge regarding the data collected. For this part of the interviews, you might prefer to interview technical staff and staff involved at operational level for your interviews.

VII. Process and outcome indicators

- What is the prime objective of the intervention? Describe.
- How do you evaluate the success of the intervention?
- How are the impacts of the intervention being monitored? Which indicators are used? Who is in charge of monitoring? What is the frequency of monitoring? Who finances the monitoring? => These questions are relevant to stakeholders for monitoring and evaluating the GAPPA interventions.

VIII. Perspectives on priorities in their contexts

What are the most important priorities to address in implementation? Is the intervention complete? Missing elements?

IX. Context information

This can include information about the socioeconomic, health, cultural, but also urban context (e.g. morphology related to ways people displace; location of households x public/ green spaces; access of transportation modes). Before the interview, there is probably already important fact gathering and document information available. The interview can be used to gather the different perspectives upon this documented information. Stakeholders from the municipalities might be well placed to answer this. An open interview might be the best option here, depending on the data that should be validated or complemented.

X. Other elements that came up in the conversations

XI. Closure

A final thank-you statement to acknowledge contributions and ask permission to be contacted again. In the informed consent form, we will ask consent for potential complementary questions after the first interview.

[1]Creswell, J. W. (2009). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications

[2] <https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/equality/equality-act-2010/protected-characteristics>: nine protected characteristics for which discrimination against should be safeguarded: Age, gender reassignment, being married or in a civil partnership, being pregnant or on maternity leave, disability, race including colour, nationality, ethnic or national origin, religion or belief, sex, sexual orientation – select relevant ones

ANNEX 2. CITY-MOVE - GENDER, INCLUSION AND DIVERSITY MONITORING FORM

This form has been developed to provide information on the representativeness of this activity.

CITY-MOVE Event	
Date	
Location	

This information will be collected and stored separately to other information collected. You are not required to provide your name or any other information that identifies who you are.

If you have any questions about this form contact [add contact details].

Please return the completed form to [add details].

Gender and Sex Identity	
What is your Gender Identity?	Indicate with X
Man	
Woman	
Non-Binary	
Other	
Prefer not to say	
Is the gender you identify with the same as your sex registered at birth?	Indicate with X
I am the same gender assigned at birth	
I am a different gender than assigned at birth	
Prefer not to say	

Age:	Years
Prefer not to say	

Do you consider yourself to have a disability?	
Yes	
No	
Prefer not to say	
<p>What is the effect or impact of your disability or health condition on your work? Please write in here:</p> <p>The information in this form is for monitoring purposes only. If you believe you need a 'reasonable adjustment', then please discuss this with</p>	

What is your current working pattern?	
Full time permanent	
Part time permanent	
Full time temporary	
Part time temporary	
Prefer not to say	

Do you have caring responsibilities? If yes, please tick all that apply	
None	
Primary carer of a child/children (under 18)	
Primary carer of disabled child/children	

Primary carer of disabled adult (18 and over)	
Primary carer of older person	
Secondary carer (another person carries out the main caring role)	
Prefer not to say	

How would you describe your national identity?
What country were you born in?

ANNEX 3. FORMAT CITY-MOVE - GENDER, INCLUSION AND DIVERSITY CHECKLIST

The questions below relate to your activities as part of the intervention. Please answer the following questions as best you can with specific reference to the intervention.

1. When preparing for activities engaging with the public (e.g. surveys, workshops, public engagement, events)		
1.1 Addressing and acknowledging identity diversity when preparing forms/surveys/workshop registration lists		
Did you add context for end users on why you gather information about their identity?	Yes	No
Tip:	Add this explicitly in one or two sentences, apart from the privacy agreements.	
Tip:	When asking about identity, make sure there is always a 'prefer not to answer' box.	
Did you consider diverse gender options in forms/surveys/workshops?	Yes	No
Tip:	Consider the question on gender to be framed as: To which gender identity do you most identify?	
Tip:	Add option for ticking: other (please specify) and do not prefer to say along with male, female	
Tip:	Ask for preferred pronoun (She/He/They)	
Tip:	Use name tags stating pronouns	
Did you consider asking for a preferred name instead or in addition to the first name?	Yes	No
Tip:	Add option for providing preferred Name after First name and Last name	
Did you consider asking for a birthplace?	Yes	No
Tip:	Add a blank short answer box.	

Did you consider asking for a country of residence?		Yes	No
Did you consider diverse dietary requirements when deciding on providing meal/snacks in your registration form?		Yes	No
Tip:	Add a question to determine dietary requirements such as 'Do you prefer:- a.)Vegetarian meal, b.)vegan meal, c.)Non-vegetarian meal d.)Have special requirements (no nuts, allergies etc.) Please specify.		
Tip:	add tags to the food that is served to indicate which food is vegetarian, vegan etc.		
1.2 Inquiring about language skills.			
Did you consider asking about the participants' language skills?		Yes	No
Tip:	Add a question on: How comfortable are you in x language? (the language in which the survey questions are/workshop is going to be held in etc.)		
Tip:	Ask local researchers to help engage with the public in the local tongue		
Tip:	Communicate in another dominant language beside the official language		
Did you consider asking a question on which language they would prefer?		Yes	No
Tip:	Add a question on: Which language do you prefer to respond in/communicate in? (this question should only be asked if there are multiple languages you can work with)		
1.3 Checking the accessibility of the activity.			
Did you consider the time of the activity (especially in-person event) in a way that is suitable for diverse and specially to encourage the unusual suspects to show up?		Yes	No
Tip:	Depending on your target audience for the activity, decide the time considerably- will they be available on weekends (and then also bring along children, if part of your target audience)?		
Tip:	Will they prefer evenings so that they can join beyond office hours? Etc.		

Tip:	Instead of assuming what the target group needs in order to attend, ask them	
Did you consider a suitable location for your target audience?	Yes	No
Tip:	If you are considering elderly for the activity perhaps make sure there are elevators if your meeting is on 5th floor or in fact find a ground floor	
Tip:	Make sure your location is accessible via public transport.	
Tip:	Go to the place where your target audience can be reached e.g. a supermarket	
Did you consider asking your target audience if they need to bring a carer with them?	Yes	No

2. When communicating via websites or social media/other publications or research/scientific articles.		
2.1 Format of communication		
Did you choose your medium based on the audience targeted?	Yes	No
Tip:	When targeting diverse audiences, use diverse media (e.g. Tik Tok, newsletter, radio, posters, paper announcements ...)	
Did you consider your target audience with visual impairments (e.g. dyslexia, (color) blindness).	Yes	No
Tip:	check the guidelines from Mental Health Europe via https://www.un.org/sites/un2.un.org/files/un_disability-inclusive_communication_guidelines.pdf	
Did you include multilingual communication based on your local context?	Yes	No
Tip:	Use all languages to communicate to the public which might be of relevance	

Did you include diverse categories in visuals/graphics?		Yes	No
Tip:	Include women, LGBTQI+, inter-racial, seniors, children/adolescents, differently-abled etc.		
2.2 Content of communication			
Did you adapt vocabulary and messaging based on the audience targeted?		Yes	No
Tip:	Scan your communication for stigmatizing language, you can use the tool from Mental Health Europe https://mhe-sme.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/MHE_WordsMatter_A4_2.pdf		
Tip:	avoid jargon, use easy language		
Did you sometimes change the order in which you mention pronouns he/she/they?		Yes	No
Tip:	You can vary that by using all Permutations and combinations - they/she/he, she/they/he etc.		
Did you include a short paragraph or disclaimer on anti-discriminatory policies?		Yes	No

ANNEX 4. TIPS FOR FACILITATING THE SAW

A. Ways to Facilitate the Discussion

- Open with a fun, non-threatening, open-ended question
 - Develop comfort with speaking in front of the group and sharing their ideas.
- Pay attention to non-verbal signals
 - Some people are listeners and might be sending a cue that they might have something to say but not confident to speak up
- Ask open-ended questions, one at a time.
 - Probe when a response is unclear.
 - “Can you say more about...” instead of “Why do you think...”
- Balance participation from all attendees
 - “Who else has something to say?” or “I would like to hear more from...”
- Redirect the discussion when it strays too far off topic.
 - “These are important and interesting points. However, can we bring the discussion back to our focus on....”
- Record the participants’ actual words as much as possible.
- Check with participants that you understand what they are saying.

B. Avoid doing the following

- Reading a script question verbatim
 - Know and rehearse how to ask questions in different ways so you appear more spontaneous and relaxed
- Finishing participant’s sentences or making assumptions about what is being said by someone.
 - Some people may be slower or take pauses as they organize their thoughts on a topic, allow them space to get their point across
- Allow one or two people to dominate or to use the SAW for their own agenda.
 - Watch the group dynamics to ensure certain people are not monopolizing the time – particularly if there is a hierarchy within an organization
- Permit side discussion
 - This can distract others from the main discussion. Be aware that some people may have hearing impairments or difficulty in focusing
- Take sides or challenge what is being said
 - Remain impartial and don’t insert yourself and your opinions into the discussion.
- Favor one participant over the others
 - It is tempting to focus on the more vocal members of the group, please avoid this
- Use jargon or technical terms
 - Avoid assuming shared knowledge as this can distance participants.

C. Bring the discussion to a close...

- End the discussion by summarizing the main points raised.
- Try to set aside some time to invite participants to reflect on the main ideas and ask if they have any additional thoughts to share.
- Thank the group for participating
- Remind them that the Participant Information Sheet contains contact details and data storage procedures.
- Let them know how the discussion results will be used.
- Let them know when and how any results / reports will be accessible to them.
- Collect and save all notes and recordings.
- Return the space as you were given it!